

Global LGBTI Internet Survey

Research Proposal

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Abstract

Background Worldwide, lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and intersex (LGBTI) people contend with high risks for HIV infection, stigma and discrimination, and for exclusion from HIV and other health services. In many low- and middle-income countries, LGBTI people are often hidden, marginalised and difficult to assess as part of general population-based surveys. Thus, assessing their exposures and outcomes and burden of HIV disease is extremely challenging. This presents a dilemma for HIV surveillance as their omission from surveillance systems leaves significant gaps in our understanding of HIV epidemics.

Objective This research project is aimed at conducting an observational, non-interventional, global cross-sectional internet survey in LGBTI participants to examine how various demographic, economic, socioecological, homophobic, psychosocial, attitudinal and behavioural variables potentiate HIV risk behaviour. We likewise aim to examine self-reported HIV prevalence, exposure to HIV related stigma and discrimination, and to study the association between these socioecological parameters and HIV care and treatment coverage in the survey participants.

Methods We imply internet sampling method to conduct the cross-sectional survey recruiting consenting adult LGBTI participants. We select internet sampling for it demonstrated to be particularly useful for hard-to-sample populations, higher number of respondents among hard-to-reach populations, faster recruitment, lower operational cost, greater level of anonymity and security provided to participants. Acknowledging selection bias, we may apply techniques, e.g. prediction modelling, to correct for the bias that results from differential access to, and use of, the internet. To safeguard the data privacy, rights and welfare of the research participants, the access to the online survey will be provided via anonymous weblink. The survey will be opened for three (3) months. Our cross-sectional study is observational by nature and it does not alter the exposure status of the consenting respondents and thus warrants minimal to no risk for the participants. We will examine the outcome and the exposures in the target population and will study their association. Our survey questionnaire provides essential components to fulfil the above objective and was developed using selected standard protocols.

Key words LGBTI, stigma, discrimination, HIV, health, socioecological, cross-sectional, behavioural, Internet, survey

Research Protocol

Introduction

Background

An understanding of HIV burden, risk factors, and coverage of prevention and treatment services is critical for combatting the HIV epidemic. Behavioural surveys assessing these parameters are integral components of a national HIV strategy and surveillance system. Countries that implement repeated behavioural surveys can monitor changes in their populations' risks for HIV, determinants of those risks, and access to prevention and treatment over time.

Many individuals at high risk for HIV are socially marginalized, experience stigma and discrimination, and may not identify themselves as such when accessing services. This makes it difficult to track them in HIV programme registers and hinders efforts to assess the effectiveness of services, their exposures and outcomes. Such populations include LGBTI people, who are at increased risk for HIV infection compared with the general population at large. The underlying reason is that HIV prevalence among their sexual or needle-sharing network is already high. Although members of the general population also engage in frequent vaginal and anal sex without condoms, their chance of having an HIV-infected partner is much lower. Additionally, global prevalence of HIV among MSM is 19 times higher than in the general population, and prevalence among transgenders is 48 times higher.

Rationale for the research

Behavioural surveillance among LGBTI populations is a priority in all epidemic settings. HIV control efforts directed at high-risk populations can have a substantial impact on the epidemic. HIV policies and programmes will be more effective if they are informed by measures of HIV prevalence among those populations, trends in their HIV-related risk behaviours, and the extent to which they access HIV and other health related services. This makes this survey a critical undertaking for monitoring the HIV epidemic and evaluating HIV control efforts.

Policies that criminalize behaviours of high-risk populations or limit their access to HIV and other health related services may further elevate their risk of acquiring and transmitting HIV. The infringement of human rights, verbal and physical violence and denial of health services associated with stigma and discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity is a demonstrated public health issue. Stigma is a central driver of morbidity and mortality at a population level[1]. Communities facing enacted sexual stigma are more likely to engage in sexual risk behaviours[2, 3]. They are less likely to adhere to their antiretroviral treatment[4] and have lower HIV testing rates[4-10]. Internalized homonegativity is associated with lower levels of HIV testing and lower levels of condom use[11]. A socio-ecological approach to health-related behaviour[12] allows for studies of the role of stigma related to sexual orientation and gender identity in their broader structural and social dimensions[1, 13, 14]. Most studies of homophobia have focused on the individual level. Being able to identify the level of homophobia at country level is important to guide public health policies as recent evidence shows that reductions in the homophobic climate are associated with improved health outcomes[15]. Data related to structural factors, such as the existence of legislation against LGBTI human rights, are generally available, although unevenly among low- and middle-income countries. But there is a lack of individual and interpersonal data on members of the LGBTI community in low- and middle-income countries.

The ultimate purpose of this research is to facilitate the collection and the analysis of socioecological data in consenting 18+ year-old LGBTI participants that could inform public health action in favour of these communities. This research proposal describes design and methods for conducting this cross-sectional web-based behavioural survey. The project is using a socioecological approach to data analysis, where the behaviour is viewed as being determined by individual, interpersonal and structural factors [12, 16-19].

Methods and Design

a) The scientific design of the study

The survey objectives

This research project is aimed to:

- conduct a cross-sectional observational, non-interventional, internet survey in consenting 18+ year-old LGBTI participants using an anonymous web-based self-administered questionnaire without any geographical restrictions;
- examine correlates of HIV infection to understand how survey variables, such as demographic, economic, socioecological, homophobic, psychosocial, attitudinal and behavioural, potentiate HIV risk behaviour and access to and uptake of HIV care and treatment services;
- provide evidence in favour of more LGBTI-inclusive health and HIV service delivery, advocacy, and policymaking.

Methods

Investigators

The research project involves the Joint United Nations Programmes on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS), the LGBT Foundation, the University of Aix-Marseille and the Medical School of the University of Minnesota. The investigators are:

- Erik Lamontagne (Senior economist, Strategic Information, UNAIDS): Principal Investigator, in charge of data collection, lead modelling and analysis.
- Sean Howell (President and CEO of The LGBT Foundation): Principal Investigator, owner of the data, in charge of data collection, modelling, analysis.
- Anna Yakusik (Economist, MSc, MBA, Strategic Information, UNAIDS): data collection, modelling, statistical analysis, quality assurance.
- Bruno Ventelou (Professor, Research Director, CNRS, University of Aix-Marseille): modelling, econometric analysis.
- Michael W. Ross (Professor, MD, PhD, MPH, MHPed, MSt and Chair of Sexual Health Education, University of Minnesota Medical School): modelling, sexuality and psychology analysis.

Scientific peer review

The research proposal has been reviewed and accepted by a scientific peer review group independent from the research project team. The comments from the scientific review group have been incorporated into the final proposal (see [appendix 1](#)).

The reviewers are (alphabetical order):

- Abhina Ahder (Associate Director, Sexuality, Gender and Rights, India HIV/AIDS Alliance)
- Martine Audibert (Director of Research, Clermont Auvergne University)
- Lee Badgett (University of Massachusetts Amherst), Asa Radix (Callen-Lorde CHC),
- Stefen Baral (Director, Key Population Program, John Hopkins University)
- Adam Bourne (Director, Australian Research Centre in Sex, Health & Society, La Trobe University)
- Richard Burzynski (Senior Adviser, Civil Society Networking, UNAIDS)
- Alex Garner (Public Policy Office, The Foundation for AIDS Research)
- Peter Ghys (Director, Strategic Information, UNAIDS)
- Asa E. Radix (Senior Director of Research and Education, Callen-Lorde Community Health Center)
- Peter Godfrey-Faussett (Scientific Adviser, UNAIDS)
- Roman Levchenko, Communication Officer, Multimedia, UNAIDS),
- Christoforos Mallouris (Senior Adviser, UNAIDS)
- Keith Sabin (Senior Adviser, Epidemiology, UNAIDS)
- Marc Sangnier (professor, Aix-Marseille School of Economics, Aix-Marseille University)
- Bruno Spire (Researcher, National Institute for Medical Research)
- Laurel Sprague (Special adviser, Community Mobilization, UNAIDS)

Target population support for the survey

We engaged with the LGBT Foundation and the members of the target population to seek their input on survey content to ensure that the survey design is consistent with on-the-ground realities, and to further encourage target population participation.

Ethical consideration

The study protocol was assessed and approved by the Research Board of Ethics of the University of Aix-Marseille, and by the WHO Research Ethics Review Committee (ERC). See [appendix 2](#).

Funding

The LGBT Foundation is supporting the research with in-kind contribution of USD 565,000. UNAIDS is providing an additional USD 45,240 from its core budget.

Timing and intervals between the survey rounds

This is the first edition of the global LGBTI survey. Future annual edition of the survey will be determined after the evaluation of the 2019 edition. A tentative timeline for this survey can be found in appendix 3.

One interest of eventual annual editions of the survey is to study the changes and the evolution of key variables over time per country. The study does not track respondents year after year. It will analyse how indicators such as well-being, mental health, HIV self-prevention, homophobia for example are evolving following changes in LGBTI legislation, in government, or in the economy at country level.

This is similar as other surveillance. It typically does not include the same participants in repeat surveys. Ideally, behavioural surveys should be conducted at intervals in order to capture changes in risk behaviours and the HIV epidemic over time. This survey can therefore serve as a baseline for any future undertakings.

Questionnaire development

The questionnaire of the survey contains established instruments for collecting survey data among key populations, such as LGBTI people, using validated questions and scores. These instruments include questions that have been used throughout the world; thus, their continued use will enable researchers to compare survey results across countries. The standardized instruments provided with these guidelines were designed to be self-administered using electronic or web-based data collection methods.

The questionnaire was built on the following four principles:

1. The process must preserve the complete anonymity of respondents. The privacy and security of respondents must be ensured at every step of the survey;
2. Questionnaire should be as short as possible. Only questions that are necessary should be included;
3. Filling out the online questionnaire should expose participants to no more than minimal risk, such as minimal discomfort, minimal anxiety;
4. Questions selected should have their reliability and validity already demonstrated and their collection should enable triangulation with other surveys.

We followed the following **key steps in questionnaire development**:

- decided on methods for questionnaire administration;
- determined investigation topics (questionnaire domains);
- developed and adapted the questionnaire;
- conducted cognitive testing;
- pre-tested the questionnaire;
- pilot tested the survey tool.

The content of the questionnaire is harmonized with standard indicators and protocol checklists used in behavioural surveillance. The questionnaire is organised as modules focused on topics, such as:

- demographics
- time preference, risk aversion
- socioeconomic status, including a question on financing hormones for transgender people
- behaviours increasing vulnerability to HIV infection (e.g. unprotected receptive anal intercourse, buying sex, selling sex, sharing nonsterile injecting equipment, alcohol and drug use)
- stigma and discrimination in the community, at workplace and health facility (sexual orientation, gender identity, HIV)
- internalized homophobia
- violence
- general health status
- mental health, including depression
- social support network, including family
- HIV prevalence, access to HIV and other health services, HIV services uptake:
 - knowledge of serostatus
 - eligible but not on HIV treatment
 - viral load suppression
 - unsuppressed viral load
 - currently in care
 - currently on antiretroviral therapy

- discussed pre-exposure prophylaxis
- use of pre-exposure prophylaxis
- health-care stigma

The consensus questionnaire (see [appendix 1](#)) consists of three modules:

- 1st module for LGBTI people, comprising 45 questions;
- 2nd module for MSM and transgender people, comprising 15 questions;
- 3rd module on HIV stigma, comprising 22 questions.

It was our preference to start and finish the survey with relatively comforting questions and statements to reduce any unforeseen discomfort in the participants.

Languages and translations

The survey will be translated in the following additional languages to increase the participation and the representativity of the LGBTI communities: Arabic, Bengali, Chinese, English, Farsi, French, Gujarati, Hindi, Japanese, Marathi, Portuguese, Russian, Spanish, Thai, Turkish, Ukrainian, and Urdu.

Translations are performed from the original English version by native speakers with knowledge in the field of HIV and LGBTI. Translated documents are retranslated to English by a second translator and discrepancies are discussed with the research team and fixed.

Data management

The [questionnaire](#) was transferred to an online survey tool, SurveyMonkey ensuring anonymized participation. The initial online transfer was subject to pre-testing. We recruited ten MSM through UNAIDS and community and asked them to work their way through the survey and to express what they were thinking, how the questions struck them, and any ideas that occurred as they proceeded. In response to user comments we adjusted very many small details of the survey, including correcting typographic errors; correcting routing errors; standardising the way individual questions were served; re-ordering modules; reordering flow of questions; rewording/clarification of question stems; reordering of response sets; and expansion of response sets. No questions (items) were cut in this process, although notes were made on what could be considered for the next round of the survey.

We performed a survey consultation to test and provide their feedback on the survey. Issues and question raised were considered and discussed with the consultees. The process resulted few minor changes to the survey. Following the processing of all comments, an item analysis was constructed, and discussion occurred among the core design team to identify the least essential questions while retaining as much topic balance as possible. This version of the survey was subject to an online time-trial.

The LGBT Foundation performed a small-scale test of the online survey with a random set of respondents, in order to estimate the average completion times, possible rejection through disproportionately skipped questions or attrition at a particular point in the completion of the questionnaire. This first online test went adequately and confirmed the interest of respondents in going through the complete survey. The average completion time spent on the survey is 11 minutes.

The online survey is expected to be rolled-out once received the clearance of the WHO ERC, tentatively end of April 2019. For rolling out the survey, we are aiming to establish a network with the following partners for the survey promotion on regional and national online networks:

- The LGBT Foundation Communications Office (<https://lgbt.foundation/>)
- UNAIDS Press Office (<http://www.unaids.org/en/resources/presscentre>);

- UNAIDS Office of Community Mobilisation (<http://www.unaids.org/en/ourwork/programmebranch/rightsgenderpreventioncommunity/mobilizationdepartment/officecommunitymobilization>);
- UNAIDS Regional Offices (<http://www.unaids.org/en/regionscountries/regions>);
- UNAIDS Country Offices (<http://www.unaids.org/en/regionscountries/countries>).

The survey will be available online for a duration of 12 weeks (3 months). Following which, unidentified data will be provided to the investigators for quality assurance, cleaning and organisation of the database.

Data analysis, use and dissemination

We selected internet sampling for it demonstrated higher number of respondents among hard-to-reach populations, faster recruitment, lower operational cost, greater level of anonymity provided to participants. Acknowledging selection bias, we may apply techniques, e.g. prediction modelling, to correct for the bias that results from differential access to, and use of, the internet. See also section (p) limitations below.

Our cross-sectional study is observational by nature and non-interventional. It does not alter the exposure status of the consenting respondents and thus warrants minimal to no risk for the participants. We will measure the outcome and the exposures in the target population and will study their association to fulfil the study objectives.

Data collected during the survey are anonymised and will be managed in a way that protects the privacy of participants and the confidentiality of the information they provided. We will take measures to prevent the unintended collection of IP addresses.

Data will be owned by the LGBT Foundation. Data will be stored on LGBT Foundation and UNAIDS in their on-premise file storage, protected with always-on real-time firewall and antivirus. Access to the anonymised individual data folder will be password protected and restricted to authorised users, after completion of a Declaration of Confidentiality and Data Privacy. Data are not and will not be monetised. Any data shared outside the survey team – such as with a third party conducting secondary analysis – will be anonymized. When disseminating results, the data will be aggregated at a higher level to ensure that the information does not enable to suspect or reveal the identity of any individual participant or group of participants.

The team will likewise work on the econometric models to answer a first set of two research questions using a socioecological approach:

- Does the homophobic climate increase the vulnerability to HIV infection for LGBTI people?
- Are perceived social and economic inequalities correlated with the incidence of HIV in LGBTI community?

The data can also be used for academic purpose, such as doctoral or post-doctoral articles by the research team. E. Lamontagne might use some of these data for a PhD thesis at Aix-Marseille University.

Country and region-specific analysis

Additional questions may be looked at following this first phase and might include country-specific questions in order to increase the relevance of HIV prevention, care and treatment interventions, zero discrimination interventions and advocacy, or human rights interventions, among others.

Feedbacks of results to communities

Dashboards on key survey indicators will be prepared at country level and posted on the [Key Population Atlas](#) web-site and on the [LGBT Foundation](#) web-site.

Results and key findings for countries and regions will be prepared in English and made available to LGBTI communities at country, regional and global levels.

Advocacy material will also be prepared by UNAIDS, the LGBTI Foundation and their partners, aiming at promotion of a more inclusive environment for LGBTI, zero discrimination campaign, “Know your status” campaign for HIV prevention, International day against homophobia (IDAHO) and others.

b) Relevance of the research to the health needs of the target population

The number of new HIV infections is decreasing worldwide but incidence is still increasing among the transgender people as well as among the gay and other men having sex with men[20]. Some surveys[14, 21], essentially in high-income countries, suggest that stigma, discrimination, homophobia are associated with poorer mental health and riskier behaviour in terms of vulnerability to HIV infection but data is lacking to study the level of this relationship in low- and middle-income countries and prohibit analysis across countries.

This research is relevant as it aims to fill this information gap in low- and middle-income countries. Findings can be used by partners, LGBTI civil society organisations and UNAIDS country offices for advocacy for more LGBTI-inclusive public health programs.

Furthermore, the survey can provide additional added value thanks to the econometric analysis of socioecological variables together with behavioural variables. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time such a multi-country data collection on lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and intersex people and analysis will be performed. If demonstrated, findings could help addressing socioeconomic inequalities correlated with increased vulnerability to HIV and STI infections.

To our knowledge, this is the first survey provided the scope, focus, and sampling design. Repeated every year this cross-sectional survey could provide useful information on the changing patterns across variables and monitor trends in exposures and outcomes in LGBTI communities. Thus, this study can become a baseline for future research. This study is sought to provide information for public health planning, monitoring, and evaluation at country, regional and global levels.

c) Sampling strategy, recruitment and voluntary informed consent

The target population of the survey are 18+ year-old LGBTI people. The survey can be accessed using a web [link](#) that will be provided at LGBTI social networks, e.g. the LGBT Foundation social networks, as well as national and regional LGBTI community networks. The survey will be opened for a duration of 3 months. Recruitment will not involve any direct recruitment and is anonymized. Participation in the survey is not incentivised. We are aware of the limitations associated to these voluntary recruitment channels and we are exploring, with LGBTI civil society organisations and UNAIDS teams at country and regional levels, all additional opportunities that could increase the participation of marginalised or remote communities and individuals.

It was considered that participants who are afraid to share information about risk behaviours or HIV status may drop out of the survey or falsify their responses. To successfully survey LGBTI people, these biases are being minimized by obtaining fully informed voluntary consent at the start of the survey from participants and ensuring their absolute confidentiality.

The informed consent of voluntary participants is summarised at the introduction of the survey and the following information is provided through a link:

- a concise description of the survey and the organization conducting it, the survey objectives, the populations being invited to participate;
- a clear indication that participation is voluntary and that participants have the right of withdrawal from the survey at any time, or skip any sensitive question/s;
- a description of the participant’s role in the survey, including duration of participation, the general nature of the questions;
- a description of the possible discomforts of participation;
- a description of the benefits to the community that are expected to come from the survey
- a description of how the findings will be made available to the respondents and the LGBTI community
- measures made to protect the privacy and confidentiality of the participant and any information that the person provides;
- documentation that the protocol was reviewed and approved by Research Ethics Review Committee (*to be completed once WHO ERC approval*);
- how the results of the survey will be used. This includes explicitly the possible use of the data for scholar purpose, such as doctoral or post-doctoral productions by the research team
- contact information and procedures for contacting the investigators in case of further queries and/or questions.

Only 18+ year-old participants can participate in the survey provided an informed consent. Participants are required to acknowledge their informed consent to enter the survey by clicking on the “OK” button (question 1, mandatory).

d) Justification of the research design

Worldwide, LGBTI people contend with exceptionally high risks for HIV infection, stigma and discrimination, and for exclusion from HIV and other health services. LGBTI people are often hidden and difficult to assess as part of general population-based surveys. Thus, assessing their exposures and outcomes and burden of HIV disease is extremely challenging and necessary. This presents a dilemma for HIV surveillance as their omission from surveillance systems leaves significant gaps in our understanding of HIV epidemics. We aim to fulfil the knowledge and apply web-based community surveying to protect person’s privacy and ensure data confidentiality during and after the survey.

e) Gender considerations relevant to the project

The online survey is about people with various sexual orientation and gender identities. We made sure the gender diversity is acknowledged and adequately reflected in the survey.

The survey was provided for review to the members of the LGBTI community with various sexual orientation and gender identities. Their feedback and comments were considered and analysed at various stages of proposal development. The comments were considered and incorporated it the final version of the questionnaire.

f) The benefits that the research will likely produce

To research participants and the LGBTI community

To applied scientific knowledge

The main benefit of the online survey is to inform how the quality of life, stigma -both perceived and enacted-, the discrimination, the social status, the economic vulnerabilities the Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender and Intersex People (LGBTI) living in low- and middle-income countries are facing is associated with their vulnerability to HIV infection and to their health status.

The analysis that will follow will support advocacy for more inclusive society and better programme design for LGBTI people in low- and middle-income countries.

g) A description of physical, social, psychological and economic risks to both individuals and communities

The safety and data security of the target population is a top priority in planning and implementation of our survey. We learned from the experience of the previous web-based surveys (e.g. EMIS, etc.), and consulted with the community-based organizations, including the LGBT Foundation. The survey will be conducted anonymously, meaning that personal identifiers will not be recorded on any forms. Unique survey codes will be used in all records and constructed without the use of personal identifying information such as any identifiable numbers.

By design this survey is a cross-sectional survey, where the investigators will measure the outcome and the exposures not altering the exposure status.

The survey instruments were previously administered in communities and proved minimal to no psychological risk for the respondents. We still acknowledge that some sensitive personal questions may trigger anxiety in some respondents. This can be the case with the following questions and/or statements:

- When was your last HIV test?
- Do you know your HIV status?
- Thinking about your last anal sex partner without any kind of HIV prevention method (that is without condom, PrEP or an undetectable viral load), did you know his HIV status?
- I feel comfortable being sexually attracted to other men.
- I have lost friends by telling them I have HIV.
- The questions of the patient health questionnaire on anxiety and depression (PHQ-4).

However, we anticipate minimal to no risk for the study participants. To monitor any related cases, we created a mailbox to respond quickly and appropriately on any query and/or event related to this survey.

h) Vulnerability to harm or to risk of exploitation

The survey does not imply any person-to-person contact. It does not collect any personal information and records are unidentifiable. The questions, taken all together, do not reveal any information that could make respondents vulnerable to harm or to risk of exploitation. The questionnaire does not use or collect geolocation data, it does not install any tracker cookies on the device of the respondents. We anticipate no harm or risk of exploitation.

i) Steps that will be taken to minimise the risks to participants, including confidentiality and privacy

As described in the section above, the online questionnaire should not entail no more than minimal risk in terms of potential stress and/or anxiety while responding to the questionnaire. The online

questionnaire compiles questions previously used in other surveys and, to the best of our knowledge, do not have any physical risk.

The data privacy and protection of information obtained from participants is important for this survey. To protect the anonymity and data privacy of the participants, the following steps have been taken:

- The study is made available to LGBTI population through a secure, SSL encrypted connection link
- The link does not require any personal identifier, email, phone or person-to-person contact
- Data in transit (ex: while responding online) are encrypted using secure TLS cryptographic protocols
- The collection tool, Survey Monkey, has [certified its compliance](#) with the EU-U.S. Privacy Shield Framework (GDPR) and Swiss-U.S. Privacy Shield
- The questionnaire does not collect any personal information. Questions, even taken all together, do not reveal any information that could enable to identify the respondents or his/her geolocation
- The collection tool does not install any targeting or advertising cookies
- IP addresses are instantly decoupled from the questionnaire, encrypted and deleted at the end of the online survey (3 months) by the survey tool
- Data records are unidentifiable

We have, to the best of our knowledge, taken all the measures to prevent any identification of the respondents by the research team as well as by any authority.

We believe we have taken all the necessary steps to ensure data privacy and to protect the confidentiality of information obtained from participants, and to protect them from social or economic discrimination or stigmatization following their participation to the online questionnaire.

Furthermore, as mentioned above, a mailbox representing the participating agencies will be provided to address any query and/or event related to this survey.

j) Adverse events

Building on earlier experiences of non-medical internet surveys (e.g. EMIS, LGBT Survey, LAMIS), the risk of adverse or serious adverse events is considered unlikely and minimal. We are taking considerate steps to safeguard confidentiality for the consenting research participants and data privacy. We anticipate that the risks to the research participants are minimal in relation to potential benefits for the LGBTI community. We will provide adequate provision for oversight and monitoring the safety and data. Also, as mentioned above, we guarantee engagement and will create a mailbox representing the participating agencies to address any query and/or event related to this survey. As such we are aimed to ensure follow up care for participants with any query and/or event related to this survey.

k) Details on how the study will be monitored

The survey is planned to be made available for completion online for 12 weeks. The research team will monitor the situation of the online questionnaire. The research team will monitor the response rate per country and will use country and regional LGBTI websites to post reminders in countries where lower responses than projected are observed.

The mail address for requesting information and right of withdrawal will be opened during all the duration of the survey. This mail address will be administered by a staff from the LGBT Foundation. This staff will not be involved in the survey itself and has completed the Declaration of Confidentiality and Data Privacy. In the case of a request of the right of withdrawal of a participant, the staff in charge will ask if the respondent accepts to reveal, confidentially, her/his IP address. The staff will contact SurveyMonkey to request that any information on the secured SurveyMonkey website, related to this IP address, including the encrypted IP is permanently removed from the survey.

I) Sample size

Various population size estimate of the different LGBTI groups are available of most low- and middle-income countries. The present survey does not pretend to collect a statistically representative sampling of these population groups. The modelling, analyses and findings of this survey will be careful in extrapolating conclusions to the entire population groups of a said country. Rather, we would like to provide statistically robust modelling of the correlates of HIV infection of the participants to the survey. This is in line with current practice in surveillance for key populations as it does not aim at a nationally representative sample of a country's population.

We set the minimum *a priori* sample size of 100 respondents per country studied, corresponding to a 0.10 (.90) probability level for a five predictors multiple regression.

The sample size for multiple regressions will vary for each equation in our model. For example, for an anticipated effect size (f^2) =0.15, a desired statistical power level of 0.90 and a probability level of 0.05 (0.95), a regression with five predictors would require a sample size of 116 respondents.

We study the combination of answers at the level of the individuals. Missing data can be estimated with multiple imputations. We use polychoric matrices for ordinal and categorical data. Multiple choice questions will be treated on a case by case basis. Detailed description of statistical methods will be provided with findings.

Exclusion and Non-qualifiers

The online questionnaire is built in three modules: A socioecological module; a module specific for men having sex with other men; and a module on HIV. Respondents must complete a module and click on 'next' in order to have her/his responses recorded. Any respondent leaving the survey before completing a module is *de facto* excluded from the survey. Respondent choosing to click on the 'exit' button are also excluded from the survey.

To increase the quality of the dataset, the research team will construct discrepancy flags which indicate whether respondents had supplied inconsistent data in different areas.

Non-qualifiers are respondents who did not meet the criteria for inclusion in the study. Non-qualifying cases include:

- Consent not provided
- Not providing a numeric value for age
- Not providing an age of 18 or higher
- Not belonging to any LGBTI groups

Non-respondents

Reflecting the experience of non-respondents is a challenge in such survey where participants are responding on a voluntary and anonymous basis. The proposal acknowledges this limitation. The report will be careful in extrapolating the findings. The report will mention the number of non-

respondents, i.e. people who did not meet the eligibility criteria and people who did not complete the survey.

m) Compensation of immediate medical or other assistance

This research is non-medical by nature and any medical or other assistance is unlikely. Still, we guarantee engagement and will create a mailbox representing the participating agencies to address any query and/or event related to this survey.

n) Incentives offered to participants

We do not use any type of incentives in this research.

o) Any information that will be provided to participants following their participation

The following elements are provided to respondents before they leave the survey:

- A thank you message for their participation and reminder of the anonymity of the survey;
- A weblink to the LGBTI Foundation where additional information on the survey, periodical updates, the general findings and next steps will be provided;
- An advocacy message encouraging participants to get tested for HIV infection.

The survey being anonymous, and the IP addresses being decoupled and encrypted automatically during the time the survey is online (3 months), there is no possibility to provide further direct information to participants after their completion of the questionnaire.

p) Limitations of the survey

This survey will be performed online. This channel is a demonstrated channel enabling higher number of respondents among hard-to-reach populations, faster recruitment, lower operational cost, and greater level of anonymity provided to participants. There are nevertheless limitations that should be acknowledged.

First is the statistical representativity of the survey. There is a selection bias in using social media and social networks. We will apply available techniques to correct for the bias that results from differential access to, and use of, the internet. Like other surveillance for key populations, the survey does not aim of a nationally representative sample of the LGBTI population of a said country.

Second is the access to the internet. Some members of the LGBTI community in low- and middle-income countries may face financial or material constraints to access the internet and thus the survey. UNAIDS Country teams will share the link of the survey with local LGBTI networks, encouraging them to see how they can facilitate an internet access to participants from their community, but it should be acknowledged that members of the LGBTI groups might not be represented.

The third limitation relates to the possible variations between languages. When available, we used validated translations of questions. When translations were not available, we made sure the translations were as close as possible from the original English version. This was achieved by performing translation and retranslation to English as proofreading. Despite of that, the specificities of the different languages make it almost impossible to ensure an exact correspondence. For

example, languages such as Japanese are highly contextual and situational and will thus require more words to describe “being comfortable”.

Finally, due to anonymity, self-reported responses such as country of residence or age cannot be verified by other means. In addition to the informed consent, the question on the age includes the choice “under 18”. Respondents selecting this answer will be considered as non-qualifiers.

Appendix 1: Online Questionnaire

The LGBT Foundation and the United Nations (UNAIDS) partnered with the Universities of Aix-Marseille and Minnesota for this quick survey on happiness, sex and quality of life. You may find more information on the survey, its purpose and first findings on: *(to be completed asap)*

Your responses are completely anonymous.

You can choose to skip any question you would prefer not to answer.

You must be at least 18-year-old to perform this survey. To be in touch, make any information requests, alert us on eventual risks, or exercise your right of withdrawal: research@foundation.lgbt.com

OK *(click is required)*

1. *I consent and wish to enter the study anonymously (*required)

- yes
- no

2. What sex were you assigned at birth?

- intersex / ambiguous
- female
- male

3. How do you define your gender identity? (tick as many as apply)

- man
- trans man (female to male)
- trans woman (male to female)
- woman
- non-binary gender (Third gender, Hijra)

4. How do you afford your hormones therapy or sex affirmation surgeries? (tick as many as apply)

- does not apply to me
- most of it is covered by the medical scheme of my country
- my private health insurance covers most of it
- from my own pocket
- I'm working extra hours to afford it
- I'm doing sex work to afford it
- I regularly sacrifice a meal to pay for it
- I can't afford it
- I don't need / don't want hormones or sex affirmation surgery for the time being
- it is illegal in my country
- other

5. How masculine or feminine are you perceived to be by those around you?

- very masculine
- masculine
- neither masculine or feminine
- feminine
- very feminine

exit

An exit button is always available at the beginning of each module. Respondent can always scroll back to it

6. What country do you currently live in? Drop down menu
7. Which of the following best reflects why you live in this country: (tick as many as apply)
- was born here, or my parents moved here
 - to study
 - to work
 - to follow a partner
 - to live more openly as gay/bi/lesbian/trans
 - to seek asylum
 - I came as a refugee
 - other
8. How old are you? Drop down menu
9. Would you say that you are open (out) as gay, lesbian, bisexual, or trans [answer 1 for not at all open (in) and answer 5 for open (out) to all or most people, you know], or answer some place in between]:
- 1 not at all open (*in*)
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5 open (out) to all or most people I know
10. In general, would you say that your health is
- excellent
 - very good
 - good
 - fair
 - poor

[Section on wellbeing and happiness (note: text in blue does not appear in the questionnaire)]

11. On the whole, I am satisfied with myself.
- strongly agree
 - agree
 - disagree
 - strongly disagree
 - I don't know
12. How willing are you to take risks, in general?
- 10 very willing
 - 9
 - 8
 - 7
 - 6
 - 5
 - 4
 - 3
 - 2
 - 1
 - 0 very unwilling

[single-item on time preference]

13. I only act to satisfy immediate concerns, figuring that I will take care of future problems that may occur at a later date

- extremely characteristic of me
- somewhat characteristic of me
- uncertain
- somewhat uncharacteristic of me
- extremely uncharacteristic of me

[sub-section: PHQ4]

For the next four questions, think back over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by the following problems:

14. Feeling down, depressed or hopeless

- not at all
- several days
- more than half the days
- nearly every day

15. Little interest or pleasure in doing things

- not at all
- several days
- more than half the days
- nearly every day

16. Feeling nervous, anxious or on edge

- not at all
- several days
- more than half the days
- nearly every day

17. Not being able to stop or control worrying

- not at all
- several days
- more than half the days
- nearly every day

18. Imagine a ladder with steps representing happiness in life.

On which step of the ladder do you stand at this time? (*Answer 1 for worst possible life for me, answer 10 for best possible life, or choose a step in between that correspond to you*)

- 10 best possible life for me
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1
- 0 worst possible life for me

[Section on social support network]

19. My family accepts me as I am

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

20. There is someone I can count on if things go wrong

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

21. There are people around me who like the same activities I do

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

22. There is someone who counts on me to lend a hand when they need it

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

[Section on body appearance]

23. I consider myself physically attractive

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

24. Most people would consider me good-looking

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

25. I think I am:

- very underweight
- somewhat underweight

- about normal weight
- somewhat overweight
- very overweight

[Section on experience of homophobic reactions]

26. Have you ever been **stared at or intimidated** because someone knew or presumed your sexual orientation or your gender identity? If yes, when was the last time?

- no, never
- yes, within the last 12 months
- yes, more than 12 months ago

27. Have you ever heard **verbal insults** directed at you because someone knew or presumed your sexual orientation or your gender identity? If yes, when was the last time?

- no, never
- yes, within the last 12 months
- yes, more than 12 months ago

28. Have you ever been **physically assaulted** because someone knew or presumed your sexual orientation or your gender identity? If yes, when was the last time?

- no, never
- yes, within the last 12 months
- yes, more than 12 months ago

[sub-section on access to healthcare services]

29. When did you last have an HIV test?

- within the last 6 months
- within the last 12 months
- more than 12 months ago
- never

30. In the last 12 months, have you avoided going to or delayed going to a health care facility for sexual health or for HIV-related services? (tick as many as apply)

- would be too risky for me
- I can't pay
- I'm embarrassed
- last time I felt stigmatised
- I'm worried someone may learn about my sexual orientation
- it's not convenient (transport, time, distance)
- I could not find the times
- it was not important to me
- I did not avoid or delay my health consultation
- other

31. Did you experience any of the following the last time you went to a health facility (tick as many as apply)

- I felt welcomed
- I had no negative experience

- verbal abuse (yelling, scolding, name calling, ...)
- physical abuse (pushing, hitting, physically hurt...)
- was given a condition (requirement) to change my sexual behaviour prior to treatment
- was given a condition (requirement) to change to change my gender identity prior to treatment
- refused to help me
- other

[sub-section on stigma & discrimination at workplace]

32. In the last 12 months, have you experienced any of the following at your current work or when you applied for a job?
(tick as many as apply)

- I faced no discrimination
- my application was refused because I am gay, bi, lesbian, trans
- I was harassed or ridiculed at the workplace
- I was not promoted because I am gay, bi, lesbian, trans
- I was told not to show me being gay, bi, lesbian, trans
- I was denied certain work-related benefits because I am gay, bi, lesbian, trans
- I was told not to work with clients
- I'm not working
- I didn't apply because I'm gay, bi, lesbian, trans
- other

33. At work, do you earn less than your nearest heterosexual (straight) counterpart who does the same kind of work

- yes
- no
- don't know
- does not apply

[Section on quality of sex]

34. Over the past three months, how satisfied are you with the quality of your sexual life?

- 10 really satisfied
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 really not satisfied

35. I would like to have sex

- a lot more often
- a little more often
- I have enough sex as is
- a little less often
- a lot less often

[Section on sociodemographic data]

36. Your relationship situation

- single
- in a relationship with a man
- in a relation with a transgender person
- in a relationship with a woman
- both with a man and a woman
- I don't know

37. Education (highest degree completed):

- none
- primary school
- secondary /high school
- university first degree
- masters/doctorate

38. Current employment status:

- employed
- self-employed
- doing casual or part-time work
- unemployed
- student
- retired
- other

[Section on economic situation]

39. Which comes closest to your feelings about your income these days?

- living really comfortably on present income
- living comfortably on present income
- neither comfortable nor struggling on present income
- struggling on present income
- really struggling on present income

40. Considering all debts or loans of whatever type, were you behind with payments by more than 3 months at any time during the last 12 months?

- never
- rarely
- occasionally
- most of the time
- all the time
- does not apply

41. How often have there been times in your life when you have lived in poverty by the standards of that time?

- never
- rarely
- occasionally
- most of the time

[Section on social situation]

42. Think of a ladder representing where people stand in **your country**

At the **top** of the ladder are the people who are the **best off**. At the **bottom** are the people who are the **worst off**. Where would you place yourself on this ladder at this moment?

- 10 among those having most money, most education and

- most respected jobs
- 9
 - 8
 - 7
 - 6
 - 5
 - 4
 - 3
 - 2
 - 1 among those having the least money, least education and least respected jobs or no job

43. Now, think of a ladder representing where people stand in your **local community**

Where would you place yourself on this ladder at this moment?

- 10 highest social standing in my community
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1 lowest social standing in my community

44. You would say you live in:

- a major city
- a medium- or small-size city
- a village
- a farm or an isolated house

45. People are different in their sexual attraction to other people. Which best describes your feelings? are you...

- attracted to other men or gay
- attracted to other women or lesbian
- attracted to both men and women or bisexual
- Straight or heterosexual
- I don't know

Note: respondents answering 1 (gay), 3 (bisexual) or 5 (I don't know) will be offered to complete module 2

Respondents answering 2 (lesbian) or 4 (straight) will be redirected to question 61 (do you know your HIV status?)

[module 2 for gays, bisexuals, transgenders or men attracted to other men]

exit

The following few questions are more specific for gay, bi, transgender and men attracted to other men

- OK (click is required)

An exit button is always available at the beginning of each module. Respondent can always scroll back to it

[Section on HIV prevention and exposure to HIV infection]

46. In the past 3 months, with how many **different** sexual partners did you have **anal sex without any kind of HIV prevention method**? That is without condoms, PrEP or an undetectable HIV viral load?
- 0
 - 1, steady
 - 1, casual
 - 2
 - 3 to 10
 - more than 10
 - Does not apply to me
47. Thinking about your last **anal sex partner without any kind of HIV prevention method** (that is without condom, PrEP or an undetectable viral load), how did it go?
- my partner fucked me (I was receptive)
 - I fucked him/her (I was insertive)
 - I both fucked and got fucked (I was both receptive and insertive)
 - does not apply to me
48. Thinking about your last **anal sex partner without any kind of HIV prevention method** (that is without condom, PrEP or an undetectable viral load), did you know his HIV status? tick as many as apply
- I didn't ask
 - s/he's HIV negative
 - s/he's HIV positive and I don't know his/her viral load
 - s/he's HIV positive AND undetectable
 - I was on PreP
 - s/he was on PreP
 - I don't remember
 - I had more than one partner and I do not know everyone's HIV status
 - does not apply to me

49. In the last 3 months, how much of the sex you've had with men has been under the influence of alcohol or any other drug?

- none of it
- almost none of it
- less than half
- about half
- more than half
- almost all of it
- all of it
- does not apply to me

50. In the past 3 months, did you share drug injecting equipment (needles, syringes) with someone else?

- yes, once
- yes, several times
- no, I don't share my equipment
- no, I don't inject drugs

51. What do you do if your potential date/sexual partner tells you they are is HIV positive? (tick as many as you like)

- I do not see them again
- I am not comfortable having sex with them
- I am comfortable having sex with them because we use a condom, I am on PrEP and/or he is undetectable
- I'm HIV positive too

52. In the last 12 months, how often have **you paid someone** to have sex with you?

- never
- 1-2
- 3-10
- 11-50
- more than 50 times

53. In the last 12 months, how often have **you been paid** to have sex

- never
- 1-2
- 3-10
- 11-50
- more than 50 times

54. I feel comfortable in gay bars

- 7 strongly agree
- 6
- 5
- 4 undecided
- 3
- 2
- 1 strongly disagree
- does not apply

55. Social situations with gay men make me feel uncomfortable

- 7 strongly agree

- 6
- 5
- 4 undecided
- 3
- 2
- 1 strongly disagree
- does not apply

56. I feel comfortable being seen in public with an obviously gay person

- 7 strongly agree
- 6
- 5
- 4 undecided
- 3
- 2
- 1 strongly disagree
- does not apply

57. I feel comfortable discussing homosexuality in a public situation

- 7 strongly agree
- 6
- 5
- 4 undecided
- 3
- 2
- 1 strongly disagree
- does not apply

58. I feel comfortable being sexually attracted to other men

- 7 strongly agree
- 6
- 5
- 4 undecided
- 3
- 2
- 1 strongly disagree
- does not apply

59. Homosexuality is morally acceptable to me

- 7 strongly agree
- 6
- 5
- 4 undecided
- 3
- 2
- 1 strongly disagree
- does not apply

60. Even if I could change my sexual orientation, I wouldn't

- 7 strongly agree

- 6
- 5
- 4 undecided
- 3
- 2
- 1 strongly disagree
- does not apply

61. Do you know your HIV status?

- I'm HIV-negative
- I'm HIV-positive
- I don't know
- I don't want to answer

- PREV (*clicking here brings the respondent to earlier module in case she/he would like to change*)
- DONE (*brings the respondent to a thank you message*)

Note: participants that have answered "I'm HIV-positive" at question will be offered to participate to module 3 (see next page)

(Thank you message)

Thank you very much for your support.

Sign up to get the results of this study and participate in future studies, your information is completely anonymous, any IP address is decoupled, encrypted and deleted at the end of the study. https://lgbt-token.org/research_signup You may share the survey via: <https://www.research.net/r/LGBTHappinessResearch>

Get tested for HIV regularly. For more information: <https://hornet.com/about/known-your-status/>

(Only participant who answered I'm HIV positive are offered to participate to module 3 below)

exit

Module 3: HIV-related stigma and discrimination

If you are HIV-positive, you may face stigma. Let's talk about it

An exit button is always available at the beginning of each module. Respondent can always scroll back to it

Choose how you feel about each statement. We understand some questions might sound disturbing. Please share your experience. It will help to create a more inclusive environment for everyone

OK (click is required)

62. I am not as comfortable as I used to be in dating since I learned I have HIV

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

63. I disclosed my HIV status on my online profile in the main app I'm using

- yes
- no

64. If no, is there any reason you don't mention your HIV status? (tick as many as apply)

- I revealed it before and couldn't meet anybody
- I'm afraid of rejection
- I say I am looking for safe sex (like with a condom) and I do not need to tell them my HIV+ status
- I don't need to mention it
- I'm undetectable
- I don't want to mention it
- other
- does not apply to me (I disclosed my HIV+ status on my profile)

65. I changed the way I have sex since I know I'm HIV positive

- yes
- no
- I don't know
- does not apply

66. Since I've known that I'm HIV-positive, I have sex with:

- people regardless of their HIV status
- only HIV-positive partners
- I don't have sex anymore
- does not apply

67. Some people avoid touching me once they know I have HIV

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

68. People I care about stopped contacting me after learning I have HIV

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

69. I have lost friends by telling them I have HIV

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

70. Telling someone I have HIV is risky

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

71. I work hard to keep my HIV a secret

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

72. I am very careful whom I tell that I have HIV

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

73. People with HIV are treated like outcasts

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

74. Most people believe a person who has HIV is dirty

- strongly agree

- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

75. Most people are uncomfortable around someone with HIV

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

76. I feel guilty because I have HIV

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

77. People's attitudes about HIV make me feel worse about myself

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

78. I feel I'm not as good a person as others because I have HIV

- strongly agree
- agree
- disagree
- strongly disagree
- I don't know

79. In the last 12 months, have you ever been excluded from social gatherings or activities (e.g., weddings, funerals, parties, clubs) because of your HIV status?

- yes, once
- yes, several times
- no
- I don't know
- it doesn't apply to me

80. Are you currently taking HIV (antiretroviral) treatment? (choose one)

- yes
- no, medication is not available at the clinic or pharmacy
- no, medication is not affordable for me
- no, I am unable to collect medications at the clinic or pharmacy
- no, I cannot tolerate medication side effects or am worried about taking the pills
- no, I do not feel treatment is needed
- no, I am worried someone would find out my HIV status
- no, I am not ready to deal with my HIV infection
- no, I am worried the healthcare workers would treat me badly or disclose my HIV status without my consent
- no, I do not qualify for treatment in my country because my CD4s are too high
- no, for other reasons

81. In the last 12 months, have you been told you have an undetectable viral load or are virally suppressed (“good viral load”)?

- yes
- no, I have not had a viral load test in the last 12 months
- no, I had a viral load test and am waiting for the results
- no, the virus was detectable/I am not virally suppressed
- I don't know what viral load or viral suppression are
- I don't have treatment

82. Living with HIV can open new horizons and positively affects us deep inside. Which of the following have been positively affected by your HIV status (tick as many as apply)

- My self confidence
 - My self-respect
 - My ability to respect others
 - My ability to cope with stress
 - My ability to better take care of my health
 - My ability to contribute to my community
 - Other
 - None of the above
-
- PREV (*clicking here brings the respondent to earlier module in case she/he would like to change*)
 - DONE (*brings the respondent to a thank you message*)

(Thank you message) see p 12

Appendix 2: Research Board of Ethics

Research Ethics Committee of Aix-Marseille University

Comité d'éthique de l'université d'Aix-Marseille

Objet : Avis du Comité d'éthique.
N/Réf dossier : 2019-14-03-004
Dossier suivi par : DRV-Audrey Janssens

Pièce(s) jointe(s) : 1 document

Marseille, le samedi 16 mars 2019

Le projet de recherche présenté par l'investigateur principal Dr. Ventelou Bruno, Directeur de recherche au Laboratoire AMSE, UMR AMU CNRS EHESS de l'Université Aix-Marseille et l'investigateur secondaire Lamontagne Erik, PhD et Economiste principal-ONUSIDA, intitulé «**Enquête sur les inégalités sociales et économiques et les facteurs de risque à l'infection au VIH de la communauté LGBT.**» a été soumis pour avis au Comité d'éthique en sa séance du jeudi 14 mars 2019.

Après audition des rapporteurs, le comité a jugé que le projet ne pose pas de problème éthique ou réglementaire.

Le Comité d'éthique de l'Université d'Aix-Marseille émet donc un avis favorable.

Le Président du Comité d'éthique

Pierre-Jean Weiller

WHO Research Ethics Review Committee

From: ERC Secretariat <no-reply-ercsec@who.int>
Sent: 29 April 2019 11:34
To: LAMONTAGNE, Erik <lamontagne@unaids.org>
Cc: YAKUSIK, Anna <Yakusika@unaids.org>
Subject: ERC.0003175 - Global LGBTI Internet Survey... (France)

Dear Colleague,

We would like to inform you that your project ERC.0003175 has received Final Approval by the Ethics Review Committee. The approval summary can be found in the database (<https://extranet.who.int/ercweb/login.php>) by clicking on: Review outcome available and then selecting the corresponding protocol at the bottom of the page.

Please note that this approval is valid for one year only. You will receive a reminder for submitting a progress report and continuing review form 2 months before the end of this approval. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us at ercsec@who.int.

Kind regards,

ERC Secretariat.

Link to the WHO-ERC database: <https://extranet.who.int/ercweb/>

MSG_C00-f_rev_ro

Appendix 3: Timeline

PART 1	May-18	June-18	July-18	August-18	September-18	October-18	November-18	December-18	January-19	February-19	March-19	April-19	May-19	June-19	July-19	August-19	September-19	October-19	November-19	December-19	January-20	February-20	March-20	April-20	May-20	June-20	July-20	August-20	September-20	October-20	
Global LGBTI Internet Survey	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	
Meetings/ Reports	Kick-off											Surveys online															peer rev.				
WP1 Review of knowledge, attitudes and practices relating to the sexual health of LGBTI people, including existing surveys	[Green bar]											[Hatched bar]																			
preparation	[Light green bar]											[Hatched bar]																			
literature review	[Light green bar]											[Hatched bar]																			
analysis	[Light green bar]											[Hatched bar]																			
WP2 Global LGBTI internet survey design	[Green bar]											[Hatched bar]																			
preparation, survey	[Light green bar]											[Hatched bar]																			
collection and review	[Light green bar]											[Hatched bar]																			
questionnaire development	[Light green bar]											[Hatched bar]																			
questionnaire refinement and sign-off	[Light green bar]											[Hatched bar]																			

PART 2	May-18	June-18	July-18	August-18	September-18	October-18	November-18	December-18	January-19	February-19	March-19	April-19	May-19	June-19	July-19	August-19	September-19	October-19	November-19	December-19	January-20	February-20	March-20	April-20	May-20	June-20	July-20	August-20	September-20	October-20
Global LGBTI Internet Survey	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31
Meetings/ Reports	Kick-off											Surveys online																peer rev.		
WP3 Global LGBTI internet survey promotion and execution development of promotion plan iterative improvement based on feedback negotiations with promotional partners monitoring of recruitment				[Green bar]									[Hatched bar]																	
WP4 Global LGBTI internet survey analysis and survey report database preparation, plan for data analysis draft survey report revision of survey report after peer review												[Hatched bar]		[Green bar]																

Appendix 4: Curriculum vitae

LAMONTAGNE, Erik

Personal Details

Gender: Male	
Country and Place of Birth: Québec Canada	
Nationality: Canada	
Are you currently a UNAIDS staff member? Yes	

Address and Contact Information	
Permanent Address: 1700 rue Isabelle-Aubert Appt 603 Québec G1M 3X9 Canada <i>Home telephone:</i> +1 418 4960819	Present Address (if different from Permanent Address): UNAIDS 20 Via Appia Geneva 1211 Switzerland <i>Telephone:</i> <i>Professional telephone:</i> +41 22 791 45 05 <i>Mobile telephone:</i> +41 79 201 18 19
Other details:	
<i>E-mail for correspondence:</i> lamontagnee@unaids.org	<i>Other e-mail address:</i> erik.lamontagne@laposte.net

Areas of Expertise

Economics, Health Expert over 10 years	Gender Equality Advanced 3 - 5 years	Public Health Specialists Advanced 6 - 10 years
--	--	---

Language Skills

Mother Tongue 1 : French	Mother Tongue 2 : -			
U.N. Proficiency Examination? Yes				
If yes, please indicate the language(s) & year(s) certificate was obtained: English (1994)				
Working Languages of UNAIDS: <table style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"> <tr> <td style="padding: 0 10px;"><i>Speaking:</i></td> <td style="padding: 0 10px;"><i>Reading:</i></td> <td style="padding: 0 10px;"><i>Writing:</i></td> </tr> </table>		<i>Speaking:</i>	<i>Reading:</i>	<i>Writing:</i>
<i>Speaking:</i>	<i>Reading:</i>	<i>Writing:</i>		

English	Advanced	Advanced	Advanced
French	Mother Tongue	Mother Tongue	Mother Tongue
Spanish	Basic	Basic	Basic
<i>Other languages:</i>			
Arabic	Advanced	Advanced	Intermediate
Portuguese	Basic	Intermediate	Basic

Education

<i>Highest Educational Degree:</i>		Master's Degree (or Equivalent)	
<p>Please indicate other educational details or studies in progress in the text box below (if applicable, publications may be entered in the Additional Information section) then</p> <p>Public Health Economics, Health economics</p>			
Educational details			
<i>Year:</i>	<i>Name of Education Institution:</i>	<i>Degree / Diploma</i>	<i>Title of degree/diploma and description of studies:</i>
2016 2019	Aix-Marseille School of Economics Marseille France	Ph. D.	Economics (ongoing) Specialised in public health econometric. developed econometric models on the economics of discrimination
2007 2012	United Nations MENA Regional Office Cairo Egypt	Certificate	Arabic
2005 2010	Ecole de Santé publique, Faculté de Médecine BP 184 54505 Vandoeuvre lès Nancy Cedex France	Diploma	Diplôme universitaire en santé publique option: Developing countries
1989 1991	Université Laval Ste-Foy, PQ Canada, G1K 7P4 Canada	M.Sc(Econ)	maîtrise en sciences économiques
1986 1989	Université Laval Ste-Foy, PQ Canada, G1K 7P4 Canada	B. Sc.	Baccalauréat en sciences économiques options: Developing Countries and Econometrics
1983 1985	Campus Notre-Dame-de-Foy Cap Rouge, Québec Canada	Diploma	Sciences

International Experience

Are you currently employed by an international organization as explained above? Yes			
<i>Organization:</i>	<i>Duty Station:</i>	<i>From:</i>	<i>Grade:</i>
AI/SIE WHO	Geneva	2010	Fixed-Term Appointment
Have you lived and/or worked outside your home country on a long-term basis (1 year or more)? Yes			
<i>Organization:</i>	<i>Duty Station:</i>	<i>From: - To:</i>	<i>Grade:</i>
MAE	Cameroon	2005 - 2007	Band 2
Commissioneuropéenne	Syria	2002 - 2005	Band 2
PNUD	Mali	1991 - 1994	Band 1
Do you have professional experience outside of your home country (e.g., short-term assignments, management responsibility, extensive business travel)? Yes			
African Region Eastern-Mediterranean Region European Region WHO HQ - Geneva			
Please specify the country and field of work: Middle East as Regional Adviser, Economist and Country Focal Point: Iran Iraq Jordan Lebanon Libya Morocco Palestine Tunisia Abkhazia, Programme officer Azerbaïdjan, Programme Officer Cameroon: Health Economist Guinea Bissau, Programme Officer Mali, Economist (junior) Mali, Programme Officer Mozambique, Programme Officer Niger, Economist Syria: Economist, social sectors Chad, Programme Officer			
A number of jobs in international organizations require that you travel extensively or are prepared to relocate. Are you willing and able to travel during the course of your duties? Yes			
If no, or with reservations, please specify:			

Present and previous employment

12 listed currently	
<i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Senior Economist	
<i>Name/address of employer:</i> UNAIDS/WHO 20 Ave Appia Geneva	<i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i> Michel Sidibé, Executive Director, UNAIDS
<i>From:-To:</i> 8/2014 - Present	
<i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i>	
<p>1. provide strategic analysis and recommendations in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - sustainability of Health and HIV financing (domestic and international resources) - modeling for estimating the economic returns of health - linking HIV and health with inequality and poverty <p>2. provide innovative strategies to position Health and HIV in the post-2015 development agenda</p>	

3. provide innovative and strategic guidance in Social Health insurance and social protection	
4. programme management and team management	
<i>Key achievements:</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - estimation of the economic returns of ending the AIDS epidemic by 2030 - estimation of the out of pocket expenditures for HIV worldwide - the economic costs of homophobia and risk of HIV transmission - to start in 2017: economic study of the demand and supply for testing technologies and antiretroviral therapy in the post-2015 environment 	
<div style="border: 1px solid red; padding: 2px;"> <i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Regional Investment and Efficiency Adviser / Team leader PPA </div>	
<i>Name/address of employer:</i> UNAIDS regional office for MENA EMRO Cairo, Egypt	<i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i> Yamina Chakkar, Regional Director
<i>From:-To:</i> 9/2010 - 7/2014	
<i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generate health economic intelligence for MENA. here, the focus is on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Sustainability of financing for HIV + Integration in health systems; + Economics of travel restriction - Develop the Shared Responsibility Agenda in the region - Perform strategic country support to Iran, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia, Palestine, Syria. Areas of focus includes National Strategy for HIV, lifting bottlenecks hindering implementation of national strategies; Financing of national response and its Sustainability - Coordinate the interventions of other UN Agencies in the field of HIV at regional level; - Participation, as resource person, in the new Unified Health Financing model lead by WHO (Geneva) - Responsible for Workplanning for the country offices; the Regional office; and the Regional Cosponsors intervention on HIV 	
<i>Key achievements:</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Macroeconomic Consequences of Renouncing to Universal Access to Antiretroviral Treatment for HIV in Africa: A Micro-Simulation Model- Social health insurance and HIV: a review of experience (peer reviewed, published 2012); - Long term sustainable financing map for 5 countries in WCA and LAC (UNAIDS papers) - Policy brief on Social Health Insurance and HIV services, in collaboration with EIP in HQ (2012) - Macroeconomic impact of HIV: the need for better modelling (peer reviewed, published 2011) - The macroeconomic consequences of renouncing to universal access to antiretroviral treatment for HIV in Africa; - various technical notes on the economics of HIV, the impact of the Economic Crisis; Financing Mechanisms; 	

TRIPS, etc. - Various technical notes on UNAIDS functional review (as resource person for MENA) - Increased efficiency at UNAIDS offices: review and focused workplanning exercises for all MENA countries + RST+ Regional Cosponsors Workplan for HIV	
<div style="border: 1px solid red; width: 10px; height: 10px; display: inline-block; margin-bottom: 5px;"></div> <i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Economist, Adviser	
<i>Name/address of employer:</i> UNAIDS 20 ave Appia 1211 Geneva 27, CH	<i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i> Robert Greener, Paul de Lay
<i>From:-To:</i> 1/2007 - 8/2010	
<i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i>	
<p>1. Provide senior strategic analysis, technical advice and policy recommendations in the economics of HIV. In particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♣ Health financing for HIV; ♣ macroeconomics of HIV at country level; ♣ social protection; and ♣ Sustainable financing (domestic resources) <p>2. Support the development of improved economic policies in the areas of vulnerability to the impacts of AIDS and the strengthening of social protection.</p> <p>3. Facilitate and coordinate economic applied research involving multiple international partners and other UN organisations.</p> <p>4. Keep abreast of economics theory and findings that relate could potentially relate to AIDS. More particularly in the sectors of health economics, microeconomics, public economics, overseas development assistance (ODA) and socio-economics.</p>	
<i>Key achievements:</i>	
<p>+ Technical analysis and policy advisory support to senior staff on economics and political issues of HIV. This economic knowledge can apply to labour economics and for vulnerable groups like women and youth in particular.</p> <p>+ Member of the World Bank/UNAIDS Economics Reference Group on HIV</p> <p>+ Research papers on particular issues with the objective to provide advocacy strategies to UNAIDS senior staff:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♣ Long term sustainable financing for HIV; ♣ Social health insurance and social protection mechanisms ♣ Impact of the economic crisis; ♣ Model for the long term economic impact of the response to HIV; ♣ The Response to HIV as a Global Public Good. <p>+ Management of research projects and teams involving universities and institutes from Africa and Latin America.:</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♣ Paper on the interaction of MDG6 with the other MDGs: getting AIDS out of isolation; ♣ Member of the UN system joint initiative on the Social protection floor; 	
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<p><i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Economist, Technical Adviser to the MoH</p>	
<p><i>Name/address of employer:</i> Ministère des Affaires étrangères 23, rue de la Pérouse 75775 Paris cedex 16</p>	<p><i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i> Jean-Pierre Lamarque</p>
<p><i>From:-To:</i> 1/2005 - 1/2007</p>	
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<p><i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i></p>	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Senior Technical Adviser to the Ministry of Public Health 2. Provide senior technical advice and policy recommendations for health financing and optimisation of resources available 3. Provide capacity building in terms of economics, planning and budgeting for civil servant from the Ministry of Health 4. Responsible for the preparation of the first debt cancellation contract (C2D) of the French government in the health sector, representing Euro 90 million. 5. Technical adviser to the Minister for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♣ Sector wide approach (SWAp) in health; ♣ Aid coordination and implementation of Paris' Declaration on aid effectiveness; ♣ Public expenditures and public health budget. 	
<p><i>Key achievements:</i></p>	
<p>+ 5 programmes representing Euro 90 millions on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♣ institutional support; ♣ AIDS; ♣ Immunisation programme; ♣ Public-Private Partnership; and ♣ Health system strengthening. <p>+ The health Mid Term Expenditures Framework (MTEF) + Preparation of the Sector Wide approach Programme (SWAP)</p>	
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<p><i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Economist, Social Sectors</p>	
<p><i>Name/address of employer:</i> Commission européenne Délégation Damas, Syrie EPSO, Commission Européenne B-11000 Bruxelles, Belgique</p>	<p><i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i> Frank Hesske, Chef de Délégation</p>

<i>From:-To: 1/2002 - 1/2005</i>	
<i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i>	
<p>1. Responsible for the preparation and the management of social development programmes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♣ Public health (Euro 30 million) this programme was the first reform programme in the health sector in Syria; ♣ Civil society (euro 10 million) under preparation ♣ Other projects in fields of cultural heritage protection (euro 9 million) <p>2. Technical adviser in health, civil society, NGO and Gender</p> <p>3. responsible for the technical and financial monitoring of projects</p>	
<i>Key achievements:</i>	
+ Implementation of the health sector modernisation programme	
<div style="border: 1px solid red; width: 10px; height: 10px; display: inline-block; vertical-align: middle;"></div> <i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Programme Officer/ Economist	
<i>Name/address of employer:</i> Handicap International 14, Ave Berthelot, 69007, Lyon France	<i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i> Jean-Baptiste Richardier
<i>From:-To: 9/1997 - 1/2002</i>	
<i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i>	
<p>1. Responsible for the preparation and implementation of development projects in Chad, Guinea-Bissau, Mali and Mozambique in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ♣ Community-based health ♣ AIDS ♣ Disability ♣ Humanitarian Demining <p>2. Person in charge of the Technical group on Economics factors</p>	
<i>Key achievements:</i>	
+ Successful design and implementation of country programmes (5 year prog) for more than euro 7 million. + Best financial coverage of all development programmes and excellent diversification of financial resources. + Development of an innovative project building development relationship between demining and territorial development.	
<i>Please indicate how many people you were responsible for:</i> 250 <i>May we contact your employer as a reference?</i> Yes	
<i>Reason for leaving:</i>	looking for career progression
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<i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Responsable d'opérations, Caucase	
<i>Name/address of employer:</i> Première Urgence 9bis rue Georges 92250 Garenne-Colombe France	<i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i> Thierry Mauricet
<i>From:-To:</i> 1/1995 - 3/1997	
<i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Préparation d'opérations d'aide humanitaire dans le Caucase dans les secteurs suivants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Aide alimentaire pour personnes extrêmement vulnérables o Réhabilitation d'urgence o Aide intégrée pour personnes extrêmement vulnérables (activités génératrices de revenus) + Administration, suivi et supervision de 15 projets (6 millions Euros). + Relations avec les donateurs, dont ECHO, Etats membres et ONU (PAM, HCR/OCHA). 	
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<i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Économiste	
<i>Name/address of employer:</i> CRC-SOGEA pour: Agence Canadienne de Développement International (ACDI) 1111, rue St-Charles Ouest, bureau 454 Longueuil, Québec, Canada	<i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i> Pierre Cholette
<i>From:-To:</i> 9/1994 - 11/1994	
<i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Analyse complète de l'offre et de la demande du secteur de l'hydraulique souterraine au Niger en vue d'en tirer un diagnostic du marché + Évaluation de l'impact socio-économique de différents scénarii de réforme de l'entreprise publique l'Office des Eaux du Sous-sol du Niger en respectant les mesures d'accompagnement des programmes d'ajustement structurel et sectoriel 	
<i>Key achievements:</i>	
analyse de l'offre et la demande de l'eau au Niger	
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<i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Économiste (JPO)	

<i>Name/address of employer:</i> PNUD Représentation du PNUD à Bamako BP. 120, Bamako, Mali	<i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i> Théodore Mpatswenumugabo
<i>From:-To:</i> 9/1991 - 7/1994	
<i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Administration et gestion de projets dans les domaines du cadrage macro-économique, des finances, du perfectionnement des agents de l'État, de la décentralisation, du processus de démocratisation + Préparation du rapport sur la coopération pour le développement, éditions 90,91 et 92/93 + Préparation du programme de gestion décentralisée du développement comprenant le cadrage macro-économique, la programmation des investissements, le suivi du Programme d'ajustement structurel et le suivi de l'impact de la dévaluation + Préparation du projet d'étude nationale de prospective à long terme (NLTPS) + Participation à la mise en oeuvre des politiques sectorielles de coopération technique + Participation à la préparation de la Conférence de Table Ronde pour le Mali qui s'est tenue en septembre 1994 à Genève 	
<i>Key achievements:</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Successful management of 4 development projects in the field of economics + Development cooperation Report 1991, 1992-93 	
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<i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Agent de recherche et de planification socio-économique	
<i>Name/address of employer:</i> Ministère de l'Industrie, du commerce et de la technologie Place d'Youville Québec Canada	<i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i> Marc Gignac
<i>From:-To:</i> 6/1991 - 9/1991	
<i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i>	
+ Études économiques de l'Accord de libre échange canado-américain sur le commerce extérieur, l'emploi, l'investissement et la productivité	
<i>Key achievements:</i>	
five econometric studies on trade and international economics, with application for Quebec Province	
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<i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Assistant de recherche	

<i>Name/address of employer:</i>	École Nationale d'administration publique Ste-Foy, Québec, Canada	<i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i>	Michel Boucher
<i>From:-To:</i> 10/1989 - 6/1991			
<i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i>			
+ Recherche économétrique sur le bien public et sur la corrélation entre le sport olympique et un bien public			
<i>Key achievements:</i>			
research paper			
<i>Exact Title of Position held:</i> Agent de recherche et de planification socio-économique			
<i>Name/address of employer:</i>	Ministère des Affaires internationales 525, Boulevard René-Lévesque Est Québec, G1R 5R9 Canada	<i>Name and title of supervisor(s):</i>	
<i>From:-To:</i> 7/1990 - 9/1990			
<i>Brief description of duties and responsibilities:</i>			
+ Participation à l'élaboration de politiques et priorités au niveau de la finance et du commerce international pour la nouvelle politique du ministère mise en oeuvre à partir de 1991.			
<i>Key achievements:</i>			
Analysis of commercial and economic comparative advantage of Quebec Province			

Additional Information

<p><i>Publications, fellowships, etc.:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The economic cost of homophobia (under submission) - The return on investment of ending the AIDS epidemic by 2030 (2019) - A socioecological measurement of homophobia for all countries and its public health impact (2018) -The Macroeconomic Consequences of Renouncing to Universal Access to Antiretroviral Treatment for HIV in Africa: A Micro-Simulation Model (2012) -Macroeconomic impact of HIV: the need for better modelling (2010) - The impact of the Economic crisis on the Response to HIV (2009)
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- The response to HIV as a Global public Good (2008) - The long term sustainable financing for HIV: What are the opportunities for Africa ? (2008)

Sean Howell

sean@foundation.lgbt
linkedin.com/in/seanhornet
San Francisco Bay Area

CEO AT LGBT FOUNDATION AND CO-FOUNDER AT HORNET

Education

Economics

Pacific Lutheran University

Graduate Public Sector Economics

The Evergreen State College

Certificate Blockchain Strategy

Saïd Business School, University of Oxford

Volunteering

Co-Chair Center for Public Health and Human Rights

Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health

Nov 2018 – Present

Board Member MPact (formerly MSMGF)

Sep 2018 – Present

Member Board Of Trustees World Affairs Council

Jan 2004 – Jan 2008

President & Co Founder

YPIN - Young Professionals International Network

Jan 2004 – Jan 2008

Experience

CEO LGBT Foundation

May 2018 – Present Netherlands

The LGBT Foundation is a not-for-profit organization that aims to deliver equality for, and advance the cause of, the LGBT community in countries across the world. We harness the power and potential of blockchain technology – alongside other technological innovations – to foster greater acceptance of the LGBT community, drive positive social change for the community's benefit, and protect vulnerable community members.

Co-Founder, Chairman & President Hornet Gay Social Networks

2010 – Present San Francisco Bay Area

With Hornet, Gays Can Now Play Safe on Gay Mobile Social Networks

Hornet Networks is gay owned, developer and distributor of the Hornet iPhone and Android Application—a location-based mobile dating and social network that lets you meet new friends based on criteria you set including geography, share photos quickly by sharing preloaded galleries, and keep notes about people you chat with. Founders and backers include the ranks of LGBT at Microsoft, LinkedIn, and Silicon Valley venture technologists. www.hornet.com

Hornet is the virtual "Third Place" of gay social networks. A "First place" is the home. The "second place" is the workplace – where people may actually spend most of their time. Third places, then, are "anchors" of community life and facilitate and foster broader, more creative interaction. All societies already have informal meeting places; what is new in modern times is the intentionality of seeking them out as vital to current societal. Hallmarks of a true "third place": free or inexpensive; while not essential, are important; highly accessible; proximate for many; involve regulars – those who habitually congregate there; welcoming and comfortable; both new friends and old should be found there.

Board of Trustee Member

PFLAG - Parents, Families and Friends of Lesbians and Gays

Jan 2003 – 2005

Parents, Families and Friends of Lesbians and Gays (PFLAG) is a national non-profit organization with over 200,000 members and supporters and over 500 affiliates in the United States. This vast grassroots network is cultivated, resourced and serviced by the PFLAG National Office, located in Washington, D.C., the national Board of Directors and 13 Regional Directors.

Our Vision.

We, the parents, families and friends of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender persons, celebrate diversity and envision a society that embraces everyone, including those of diverse sexual orientations and gender identities. Only with respect, dignity and equality for all will we reach our full potential as human beings, individually and collectively. PFLAG welcomes the participation and support of all who share in, and hope to realize this vision.

Anna Yakusik

Phone: 41.78.734.0103 •• E-Mail: annayakusik@gmail.com 10 Rue Emile-Yung •• Geneva 1205, Switzerland
US Permanent Resident

SUMMARY

Technical Officer at UNAIDS, with 10 years of work experience, including more than 7 years related to public health, health financing, and health economics. Designed and managed health economics studies in resource-poor settings, with deep methodological expertise in cost-effectiveness analysis, resource tracking, and economic modeling. Professional experience working with multilateral institutions and diverse research teams. Carried out research projects in Eastern Europe and Central Asia, the Caribbean, Asia, and various countries in sub-Saharan Africa. Experience writing analytical reports and reviews, and leading presentations at the national and international level.

EDUCATION

2010-2012 - MA, Business Administration, European Humanities University, Lithuania. Areas of concentration: public finance and policy, economic analysis and health economics.

2007-2008 – MA, Economics, Brest State Technical University, School of Economics, Belarus. Areas of concentration: economic theory, public economics, public finance and policy, applied econometrics.

2000-2005 - BSc Economics (Honours), Brest State Technical University, School of Economics, Belarus. Areas of concentration: economic history, economic theory, advanced macro and microeconomics, econometrics and economic statistics, computer science.

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

2013 – Present, Technical Officer, Economics and Evaluation Division, Strategic Information and Evaluation Department, UNAIDS Secretariat, Geneva, Switzerland

Contribute to the development of approaches, normative guidance, tools, and indicators to monitor resources available for HIV&AIDS. Assess health and disease spending data and make recommendations on improving its availability and quality. In collaboration with UNAIDS country teams, liaise with technical partners to improve tracking of health and disease spending data. Develop and assess strategic options, draw strategic implications, and engage in policy discussions on financial sustainability of HIV programs in low- and middle-income countries. Support UNAIDS Secretariat, country teams and regional offices with strategic information activities and quantitative analyses on health and disease financing, leveraging domestic resources, and innovative financing. Contributes to capacity building of UNAIDS regional and country teams. Share best practices and lessons learned across countries. Foster effective relationships and partnerships with country officials and partner agencies; and represent UNAIDS in sustainability and expenditure tracking related forums.

INDEPENDENT CONSULTANCIES

- 2012: Consultancy for the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Belarus Country Office. Investment case study with pilot application of the Optima mathematical optimization model for

HIV&AIDS (optimamodel.com) developed by the University of New South Wales (UNSW) with the World Bank. The analysis included strategies for efficient resource allocation and innovative financing mechanisms.

- 2012: Consultancy for the UNDP Belarus Country Office, Programme Implementation Unit of the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria. Resource tracking for HIV, costing. Financial gap analysis for HIV for the standard Global Fund concept note applications.
- 2012: GRM International, Consultancy for Tajikistan. Resource tracking for HIV, costing. Capacity building for the National AIDS Commission. Capacity building for the national technical working group.
- 2011-2012: Consultancy for the UNAIDS China Country Office. Resource tracking for HIV, costing. Capacity building workshops for Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention, UNAIDS China, and Beijing University School of Economics (Beijing, Dehong). Facilitation of national and regional level trainings. Capacity building for the national technical working group.
- 2011: Consultancy for the UNAIDS Tajikistan Country Office. Technical report on HIV funding flows in Tajikistan for 2008-2009.
- 2008-2011: Multiple consultancies for the UNAIDS Belarus Country Office. Resource tracking for HIV, costing. Multiple capacity building workshops for the Ministry of Health, the National AIDS Commission, the UNDP Programme Implementation Unit of the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria, civil society and non-governmental organizations. Training of national technical working group. Financial gap analysis for HIV for the standard Global Fund concept note applications. Cost-effectiveness evaluation of needle and syringe exchange programmes for people who inject drugs.
- 2010: Consultancy for the International HIV/AIDS Alliance, Ukraine Country Office. Resource tracking for HIV. Capacity building workshops for the National AIDS Commission, and Ukraine Country Office of the International HIV/AIDS Alliance.
- 2009-2011: Multiple consultancies for the UNDP, Programme Implementation Unit of the Global Fund, AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria grants, Tajikistan Country Office. Resource tracking for HIV, and TB. Multiple capacity building workshops for the National AIDS Commission, the UNDP Programme Implementation Unit of the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria, the TB Control Programme, civil society and non-governmental organizations. Budgeting of HIV national strategic plan. Financial gap analysis for HIV, and TB for the standard Global Fund concept note applications.
- 2009, 2010: UNAIDS Secretariat Geneva, Consultancy for Belarus. Evaluation of the impact of the global economic crisis on HIV prevention and treatment programs in Belarus.

TEACHING EXPERIENCE

2006 – 2009 Brest State Technical University, School of Economics, Belarus. University instructor for undergraduate students at the School of Economics. Coursework: Business Law, Applied Taxation, Public Finance, Mathematical Statistics.

SELECTED PUBLICATIONS

- "Financing and Costing." In: Consolidated Strategic Information Guidelines for HIV in the Health Sector, 63-64, 205207, 274-275. Geneva: World Health Organization (WHO). 2015
http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/164716/1/9789241508759_eng.pdf?ua=1&ua=1
- "The Financing Lesson." In: How AIDS Changed Everything — MDG6: 15 Years, 15 Lessons of Hope from the AIDS Response, 187-221. Geneva: UNAIDS. 2015

- "Target 6. Close the Global Aids Resource Gap by 2015 and Reach Annual Global Investment of US\$22–24 Billion in Low- and Middle-income Countries." In: Global AIDS Response Progress Reporting 2015, 88-90, 110-117. Geneva: UNAIDS. 2015 http://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/media_asset/JC2702_GARPR2015guidelines_en.pdf
- Duo Shan, Jiangping Sun, Anna Yakusik, et al. Total HIV/AIDS Expenditures in Dehong Prefecture, Yunnan Province in 2010: The First Systematic Evaluation of Both Health and Non-Health Related HIV/AIDS Expenditures in China. PLOS ONE. 2013 <http://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0068006>
- David P. Wilson, Anna Yakusik, et al. HIV resource needs, efficient allocation and resource mobilization for the Republic of Belarus. UNAIDS, UNDP, UNSW, and Abt Associates. 2013 <http://optimamodel.com/pubs/belarusreport.pdf>
- "Close the Global AIDS Resource Gap." In Global Report: UNAIDS Report on the Global AIDS Epidemic 2013, 68-77. Geneva: UNAIDS. 2013 http://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/media_asset/UNAIDS_Global_Report_2013_en_1.pdf
- Smart Investments. Geneva: UNAIDS. 2013 http://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/media_asset/20131130_smart-investments_en_1.pdf Anna Yakusik, et al. National AIDS Spending Assessment in Dehong Prefecture of Yunnan Province, China. China CDC, UNAIDS, Beijing University. 2012 http://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/documents/china_2010_en.pdf
- Anna Yakusik, et al. Resource Flows and Levels of Spending for the Fight against Tuberculosis in Tajikistan, 2010. Tajikistan TB Control Programme, UNDP. 2012. Available upon request.
- Anna Yakusik, et al. National AIDS Spending Assessment in Belarus for the period of 2008-2012. Belarus national AIDS commission, UNAIDS, UNDP. 2012. http://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/documents/belarus_20082011_en.pdf
- Valentina I Kachan, Alena I Tkachova, Eleanora Gvozdeva, Ilona Urbanovich, Anna Yakusik, Peter Amico, and Carlos Avila. Resource flows and levels of spending for the response to HIV/AIDS in Belarus. BMC research notes. 2011 <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3156755/>
- Anna Yakusik, et al. National AIDS Spending Assessment in Tajikistan for the period of 2008-2009. Tajikistan national AIDS commission, UNAIDS, UNDP. 2011. http://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/en/media/unaids/contentassets/dataimport/pub/report/2008/NASA_TAJIKI_STAN_2008-2009_en.pdf

LANGUAGES AND SKILLS

Fluent English and native Russian; intermediate French
MS Office, Stata, Matlab

Bruno Ventelou

AMSE
5/9 bd Bourdet
Marseille
13001
FRANCE

+33 (0)4 13 55 25 82
bruno.ventelou@univ-amu.fr
BORN 1967

Position

January 2004 -
present)

Aix Marseille School of Economics (AMSE) ; CNRS, Aix-Marseille University, France
Research professor

Member of Collège des Economistes de la Santé, Member of Commission des comptes de la Santé, Laureate of Programme AVENIR de l'Inserm, advisor at Observatoire Régional de la Santé PACA, advisor at MGEN research council.

Research

Themes

Health Economics ; Macroeconomics ; History of Keynesian Economics

Areas of expertise in health economics:

- . **Production of health, health behaviours & policy interventions**
- . **Supply of health services**
- . **Health care financing & expenditures**
- . **Evaluation of policy, programs and health system performance**

Recent Publications

1. Cortaredona, S., & **Ventelou, B.** (2017). The extra cost of comorbidity: multiple illnesses and the economic burden of non-communicable diseases. *BMC Medicine*, 15(1), 216.
2. Treibich, C., Lescher, S., Sagaon-Teyssier, L., and **Ventelou, B.** (2017). The expected and unexpected benefits of dispensing the exact number of pills, *PLoS-ONE*, 12(9) : e0184420.
3. Nay O., Béjean S., Benamouzig, D., Bergeron H., P. Castel., & **Ventelou B.** (2016). Achieving universal health coverage in France: policy reforms and the challenge of inequalities. *The Lancet*, online: May 2, 2016, Vol 387, No. 10034, p2236–2249, 28 May 2016
4. Tchewonpi-Kankeu, H., & **Ventelou, B.** (2016). Socioeconomic inequalities in informal payments for health care: An assessment of the 'Robin Hood' hypothesis in 33 African countries. *Social Science & Medicine*, 151(February), 173-186.
5. Weeks, W. B., Jardin, M., Dufour, J. C., Paraponaris, A., & **Ventelou, B.** (2014). Geographic Variation in Admissions for Knee Replacement, Hip Replacement, and Hip Fracture in France: Evidence of Supplier-induced Demand in For-Profit and Not-for-Profit Hospitals. *Medical care*, 52(10), 909-917.
6. Arrighi, Y., Abu-Zaineh, M., & **Ventelou, B.** (2015). To Count or Not to Count Deaths: Reranking Effects in Health Distribution Evaluation. *Health economics*, 24(2), 193-205.
7. Woode, M. E., Nourry, C., & **Ventelou, B.** (2014). Childhood preventive care, adult healthcare and economic growth: The role of healthcare financing. *Economics Letters*, 124(1), 41-47.

Books:

- (1) *Millennial Keynes : The Origins, Development and Future of Keynesian economics*, M.E. Sharpe Publisher, New York + ed Paperback. Traduction et préface de G. Nowell, 2004.
- (2) *Au delà de la rareté, la croissance économique comme construction sociale*, Albin-Michel, Paris, septembre 2001. Sélectionné pour les journées 2001 du *Livre d'Economie* au Sénat.

Michael Wallis ROSS

Address

Program in Human Sexuality,
Department of Family Medicine and Community Health,
University of Minnesota,
1300 South 2nd Street, Minneapolis MN 55454, U.S.A.

Tel: Office: 612-624-4749; Secretary: 612-625-1500.

Citizenships

New Zealand, Australia, United States of America.

Education

Massey University, New Zealand
(Faculty of Arts: in Psychology) B.A. and (1973)
B.A.(Hons) (1974)

University of the State of New York,
Albany, New York, U.S.A B.S. (1976)
(Faculty of Science: in Medical Sociology)

Victoria University of Wellington,
New Zealand M.A. (1975)
(Faculty of Arts: in Social-Clinical Psychology)

University of New England, Australia
(Faculty of Education: in Adult Education) Diploma in
Tertiary Ed. (1984)

University of Melbourne, Australia
(Faculty of Science: in Health Psychology) Ph.D. (1980)

University of Adelaide, Australia
(Faculty of Medicine: in Epidemiology) M.P.H. (1989)

University of New South Wales, Australia
(Faculty of Medicine: in Health Personnel Education) M.H.P.Ed. (1991)

Prince of Songkla University, Thailand
(Faculty of Medicine: in Tropical Clinical STDs) Diploma in STDs
(1992)

Malmö University, Sweden.
(Faculty of Medical Sciences: in Health and Society) *Medicinae Doctor: M.D.*
(2006)

University of Cambridge, UK
(Faculty of Law: in Prison Studies) Diploma in
Applied Criminology
(with Commendation)
(2003)

University of Cambridge, UK M.St. (2004)
(Faculty of Law: in Applied Criminology) (Prize for top student)

Post Doctoral Institute of Sociology, University of Helsinki, Finland (1978, 1980)

Employment **Professor and Joycelyn Elders Chair of Sexual Health Education**
Department of Family Medicine and Community Health
University of Minnesota **2014 –**

Professor (with tenure)
School of Public Health
Center for Health Promotion and Prevention Research
The University of Texas at Houston 1993 – 2014
and

Professor (Cross-appointment)
Infectious Diseases, School of Medicine
The University of Texas at Houston 1996 – 2014

Director, University of New South Wales Unit
National Centre in HIV Social Research
School of Community Medicine
(rank of Associate Professor) 1990 - 1993

*Co-ordinator, WHO International Training Courses
on Counseling and Risk Reduction in HIV Infection
and Disease, WHO Regional Training Centre,
University of New South Wales 1990 - 1993

National Health and Medical Research Council
Senior Research Fellow
The Sydney Hospital 1989 - 1990

*Occasional World Health Organisation Consultant,
Global Programme on AIDS
Geneva 1989 -

Director, Research, Evaluation and Epidemiology
STD/AIDS Services
South Australian Health Commission 1988 - 1989

STD/AIDS Programme Co-ordinator

South Australian Health Commission	1985 - 1988
Senior Demonstrator (Grade 2) in Psychiatry Flinders University of South Australia	1978 - 1985
Tutor in Psychology University of Melbourne, Australia	1977 - 1978
*Unpaid co-appointments	

Honorary Positions

Clinical Lecturer in Venereology University of Sydney	1989 - 1993
Visiting Fellow National Drug and Alcohol Research Centre UNSW	1991 - 1993
Clinical Senior Lecturer in Psychiatry and Community Medicine Flinders University of South Australia Medical School	1985 - 1989
Senior Clinical Psychologist (PSC-3) Flinders Medical Centre	1978 - 1989
Visiting Lecturer, Glenside Psychiatric Hospital	1980 – 1989
Chair, Fellows Committee, Division 44 American Psychological Association	2000 – 2003
Honorary Professor of Health Sciences, University of Sydney	2006 –
Docent, Faculty of Health and Society Malmö University, Sweden	2009 –

Memberships

Fellow, New Zealand Psychological Society
 Fellow, British Psychological Society
 Fellow, American Psychological Association (Division 44)
 Fellow, Royal Society of Arts
 Fellow, Royal Society of Public Health
 Fellow, Society of Antiquaries of Scotland
 Fellow, Society for the Scientific Study of Sexuality; (International Board
 Member, 1991-1993; Midcontinent region Board member, 1998-1999; President

Elect, 1999; President, 2000-2001, past-president, 2001-2002)
Honorary Fellow, Royal Australasian College of Physicians, Chapter of Sexual
Health Medicine
Liveryman, Worshipful Company of Scriveners of London, and Freeman of the City
of London

Awards and Honours

Faculty of Arts Travelling Scholarship,
University of Melbourne, 1977
(to Stockholm and Göteborg Universities for doctoral research).

Faculty of Arts Travelling Scholarship, 1978
(to University of Helsinki for post-doctoral research).

Hugo Beigel Award of the Society for the Scientific Study of Sex, U.S.A. (annual
international award for the most important contribution to sexuality research), 1980.

Delivered first Michael Q. Petersen Memorial Lecture to American Physicians for
Human Rights, Chicago, August 1984, on "Social and Political Aspects of
Homosexual Health Care".

Keynote Address, "Homosexuality beyond Disease" conference, Amsterdam,
December 1987, on "The Future of the Study of Homosexuality".

The Newman Award for Excellence in AIDS Research, Australian National Council
on AIDS (annual award for research excellence), 1989.

Keynote Address, International Academy of Sex Research, Uppsala, Sweden,
August 1990, on "Social and Cultural Influences on Male Homosexual Behaviour".

Plenary Address, Society for the Scientific Study of Sex, Annual Conference,
Chicago, November 1993, on "Attitudes toward Condoms in Homosexual Men".

US Surgeon-General's Exemplary Service Award, 2001, for co-writing the "Surgeon-
General's Call to Action to Promote Sexual Health and Responsible Sexual
Behavior".

Alfred C. Kinsey Award, Society for the Scientific Study of Sexuality, 2004, for
scientific achievement in the field of sexology.

Distinguished Scientific Achievement Award, 2005, Society for the Scientific Study
of Sexuality, for contributions which have advanced the understanding of human
sexual behavior and promoted the study of sexuality.

Current Licensure/Registration

Chartered Psychologist, United Kingdom Registration # 16754 (since 1988)

Research Grants

Australia:

University of Melbourne research grants (2)	1977 1978	\$300 \$500
Flinders University research grants (3)	1980 1981 1982	\$2,500 \$420 \$860
Glenside Hospital Research Foundation grant (Measurement of Depression)	1980	\$1,000
South Australian Health Commission grant (Psychoneuroimmunology in male homosexuals: with Dr. P.A. Drew)	1983	\$25,720
National Health and Medical Research Council (Precursors of AIDS in Male Homosexuals: with Dr. P.A. Drew)	1984	\$23,500
National Health and Medical Research Council (Assessment of AIDS Risks and the Cognitive, Informational and Behavioural components of AIDS)	1986	\$83,864
South Australian Health Commission Grant (Attitudes to condom use in heterosexual men and women: with Dr S. Chapman)	1986	\$5,000
National Health and Medical Research Council (Knowledge of AIDS and risk behaviours in four ethnic minority groups: with Dr K. Rigby et al)	1988	\$72,900
National Health and Medical	1989	\$42,300

Research Council (Effects of meditation on the immune system of HIV infected men: with Drs J. Condon & J. Need)		
Newman Award for AIDS Research	1989	\$12,500
Committee on AIDS Research Grants (Situational contributors to and rationalisations used to justify unsafe sex: with Dr R. Gold & Mr B. Parnell)	1990	\$47,400
World Health Organisation (Indirect methods of enumeration of groups particularly at risk of HIV infection in an urban environment: with Drs R. Taylor, B. Donovan, J. Kaldor, & Prof. J. Darroch)	1990	\$70,060
Committee on AIDS Research Grants (Decision making and determinants of risk behaviours for HIV infection)	1991	\$44,059
Committee on AIDS Research Grants (Emotional Well-being of people bereaved by AIDS: with Dr B. Kelly & Prof. B. Raphael)	1991	\$51,265
Committee on AIDS Research Grants (National Injecting Drug and AIDS Study: with Drs A. Wodak, B. Monheit, Prof. D. Hawks, Ms W. Loxley, & Mr A Buzolic)	1991	\$254,270
Research into Drug Abuse Grants (Determinants of risk-taking among methadone maintenance clients: with Prof. N. Heather, Prof W. Hall, & Dr S. Darke)	1992	\$94,812
Committee on AIDS Research Grants (National Injecting Drug and AIDS Study)	1992	\$92,000

U.S.A:

National Institutes for Health: HIV/AIDS Risks and Education Component, Research Centers for Minority Institutions Grants (through Texas Southern University. James Essien, Co-Principal Investigator) \$252,000/5 years (20% time)

American AIDS Foundation: HIV Prevention Case Management for Gay/Lesbian Street Youth (through Houston Institute for the Protection of Youth (Tracy Brown, Co-Principal Investigator) \$79,365/2 years (5% time)

Health Resources Services Administration: Learning, Empowerment Advocacy Participation (Jim Halloran, Co-Principal Investigator) \$55,532/1 year (5% time)

Health Resources Services Administration: Evaluation of Texas/Oklahoma AIDS ETC Dental Training Project, Consultant (Deborah Brimlow, Principal Investigator) \$10,000/1 year

Health Resources Services Administration: AIDS Education & Training Center for Texas and Oklahoma, Evaluation Consultant (Richard Grimes, Principal investigator) \$13,346=10% time/5 years

City of Houston - Health & Human Services: Evaluation of City's HIV Prevention Planning Process (Co-Evaluator with Deborah Scott) \$15,000/2 years

National Institute for Drug Abuse: Tuberculosis Spread in Drug Users in Houston, TX (James M. Musser, Baylor College of Medicine, Principal Investigator) \$5,695,700/5 years (5% time)

Centers for Disease Control: STD/HIV Behavioral Training Center (jointly with Dallas County Health Department) (Michael W. Ross, Principal Investigator) \$1,300,000/5 years (25% time)

Centers for Disease Control: Syphilis control in Houston (Michael W. Ross, Principal Investigator) \$2,000,000/5 years (30% time)

Texas Commission on Alcohol and Drug Abuse: STDs in crack users (Michael W. Ross, Principal Investigator) \$28,000/1 year

Texas Commission on Alcohol and Drug Abuse: STDs in drug users in treatment (Michael W. Ross, Principal Investigator) \$32,000/1 year

National Institute of Drug Abuse: Positive Choices Research Project (Mark L. Williams, Principal Investigator) \$1,835,000/5 years (20% time)

National Institutes of Health: Social network characteristics of a highly active HIV/STD core group (Mark L. Williams, Principal Investigator) \$1,669,000/5 years (20% time)

National Institutes of Health: Videotape-based HIV prevention (James Essien, Principal Investigator). Subcontract \$535,000/4 years (15% time)

Centers for Disease Control: Behavioral Surveillance for gonorrhea in Houston (Michael W. Ross, Principal Investigator) \$447,000/3 years (40% time)

CDC (through Association of Schools of Public Health): Identifying non-gay identifying men who have sex with men on the Internet (Michael W. Ross, Principal Investigator). \$400,000/2 years (20% time)

Centers for Disease Control: Tanzanian AIDS Prevention Project (Mark L. Williams, Principal Investigator) \$167,195/2 years (9% time).

National Institutes of Health: HIV, Risk Behaviors and Stigma in in High Risk Tanzanian Men (Michael W. Ross, Principal investigator). \$256,017/2 years (15% time)

University Teaching

Flinders University - School of Medicine

- | | |
|-------------|--|
| 1978 - 1985 | Co-ordinator, Psychosocial-Psychobiological Systems Course, Year III Medicine, Flinders University |
| 1979 - 1988 | Co-ordinating Lecturer, Introduction to Sexual Medicine, Core Topic, Year IV Medicine, Flinders University |
| 1979 - 1980 | Bridging courses in Sexual Medicine, Years IV to VI Medicine, Flinders University |
| 1980 - 1988 | Lecturer to psychiatric trainees, Year I & Year III Boards for Royal Australian and New Zealand College of Psychiatrists (co-ordinator of Clinical Psychology course). |
| 1979 - 1985 | Electives offered in sexual medicine (with Dr. J.A.Need), psychiatry (gender problems and transsexualism), Flinders University |
| 1982 - 1985 | Co-ordinator (with Dr. M. McLaughlin), General Issues in Medicine, Year IV Medicine, Flinders University |

University of New South Wales - School of Community Medicine

- | | |
|-------------|--|
| 1989 - 1993 | Occasional lectures, MMed(Ven) and MPH courses, University of Sydney & MCH course, University of New South Wales |
|-------------|--|

University of Texas - School of Public Health

- | | |
|-------------|--|
| 1993 - 1996 | Addictive Behaviors (Co-taught with Dr David Martin), 4 credit hours |
|-------------|--|

1994 - 2000	Advanced Theory in Health Promotion (Co-taught with Drs Alfred McAlister and María Fernández-Esquer), 3 credit hours
1994 -	Genital, Sexual and Reproductive Public Health (Sole teacher), 3 credit hours
1995 - 1999	Social Theory and Health (Co-taught with faculty of Behavioral Sciences and Management and Policy Sciences), 2 credit hours
2000 - 2003	International Health Promotion (Co-taught with Drs Alfred McAlister and María Fernández-Esquer), 3 credit hours
2006 - 2014	AIDS and Africa (Co-taught with Dr Sheryl McCurdy), 3 credit hours
2007 - 2014	Introduction to Health Promotion and Behavioral Sciences (Co-taught with Dr Alfred McAlister), 3 credit hours

University of Minnesota – School of Medicine

2015 –	MS-1 Sexual Health
2017 –	MS-4 LGBT Elective

Clinical Duties

1979 - 1988	Coordinator, Gender Clinic, Flinders Medical Centre
1985 - 1988	Coordinator, AIDS Clinic, South Australian Health Commission

Committees

Flinders University **University**

1980 - 1982	Academic Committee
1980 - 1982	Animal Experimentation Ethics Review Committee

Medical School

1979 - 1985	Third Year Committee
1979 - 1985	Third Year Examinations Board
1979 - 1989	Fourth Year Committee
1979 - 1989	Fourth Year Examinations Board
1980 - 1985	Standing Committee

- 1980 - 1988 Research Committee
- 1980 - 1985 Admissions Committee
- 1985 - 1988 Curriculum Evaluation Committee

University of Texas - School of Public Health

- 1993 - 2001 Admissions Committee
- 1994 - 2000 Distance Learning Working Group
(and Subcommittee for Course Design and Presentation)
- 1995-1997,
2000-2002 Convenor (Head of Department), Health Promotion/Behavioral Sciences
- 1999 - Committee, Delta Omega (University of Texas chapter)
(Public Health honors society)

Houston Health Science Center

- 1996 - 1998 Infectious Diseases Committee
- 1997- 2002 Institutional Biosafety Committee

Houston Community Service

- 1994- 2000 Member, AIDS Care Team, St Anne's Catholic Church
- 1994 - 1997 Board Member, Hope is Victory (services to African American
people with HIV disease)
- 1995 - 1997 Harris County (Houston) Ryan White Planning Council
Case Management subcommittee
Cultural Sensitivity Training workgroup
Client Satisfaction Survey workgroup
Minority Sensitivity and RFP Review workgroup
- 1995 - 2005 Board, Kolbe Project (Franciscan NGO for people with HIV disease)
- 1995 - 2014 Community Research Risk Protection Committee, Montrose/Legacy Clinic
(Institutional Review Board for Houston Clinical Research Network)
- 1997 - 2014 Member, Research Advisory Group, Houston Area Women's Center
- 1997 - 2006 Board Member, Saving Lives through Alternate Options (Minority public
health interventions CBO) (Board chair 2001 - 2006)

2006 - 2013	Trustee, Christus - Stehlin Foundation for Cancer Research
2009 - 2012	Member, Houston-Harris County Office of Drug Policy Advisory Committee
2011 - 2014	Board Member, LIVE (NGO working to reduce HIV-related stigma)
2014 - 2017	Board member, Human Research Committee, American Psychological Association (APA)
2012 -	Member National Institute of Health Study Section ZRG1 AARR-C(22)

Australia: State & National

1979 - 1993	Secretary, Australian and New Zealand Medical Committee on Transsexualism
1983 - 1989	Secretary, South Australian Advisory Committee on AIDS
1983 - 1984	Secretary, National Venereology Council of Australia
1983 - 1989	Delegate to Council, National Venereology Council of Australia
1985 - 1987	Member, South Australian Animal Welfare Advisory Committee
1985 - 1988	Member, National AIDS Task Force
1986 - 1988	Member, National Advisory Committee on AIDS
1988 - 1990	Member, National AIDS Forum

International

1989 - 1990	Member, WHO Technical Working group on Bisexuality and HIV/AIDS
1989 - 1990	Member, WHO Technical Working Group on Responses of Health Workers to HIV/AIDS
1993 - 1997	Chair, HIV/AIDS Committee, Society for the Scientific Study of Sexuality
1997 - 1999	Chair, Publications Committee, Society for the Scientific Study of Sexuality
2000 - 2001	President, Society for the Scientific Study of Sexuality (President-elect 1999, Past president, 2002)

<u>Editorial</u>	Board of <u>AIDS Care</u> (American Editor, 1994 - 2006)	1990 - 2010
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Board of <u>Journal of Psychology and Human Sexuality</u> (from 2007, becomes <u>International Journal of Sexual Health</u>)	1989 –
Board of <u>Journal of Homosexuality</u> ,	1983 -
Board of <u>Sexological Review</u>	1992 - 2000
Board of <u>Venereology</u>	1992 - 2001
Board of <u>International Journal of Intercultural Relations</u>	1992 - 2005
Board of <u>International Journal of Transgenderism</u>	1997-
Board of book series <u>Contemporary Perspectives on Lesbian, Gay and Bisexual Psychology</u> , APA Books	2001-
Board of <u>Counseling, Psychotherapy and Health</u>	2004-
Board of <u>Journal of Correctional Health Care</u>	2005-
Board of <u>Psychology and Sexuality</u>	2009-
Chair, Publications Committee, Society for the Scientific Study of Sexuality (responsible for oversight of <u>Journal of Sex Research</u> and <u>Annual Review of Sex Research</u>)	1997-2000.
Board of <u>Social Science and Medicine</u>	2003-2006
Board of <u>Sexuality Research and Social Policy</u>	2005-2012
Board of <u>Journal of LGBT Health Research</u>	2005-2009

Aviation Training:

Sydney Aerobatic School

Licences -- Australian and US Private Pilot, land/single, both current

Aircraft ratings -- Avions Pierre Robin 2160 Aerobin, Bellanca 8KCAB Super Decathlon; and Pitts S-2A Special (all with unrestricted aerobatic ratings)

Publications

Impact Analytics (Manifold, 12/20/18)

h-Index	H(fl)-Index	Total Publications	First/Last Author Publications	Total Citations	First/Last Author Citations
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50	39	470	286	9385	5285
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PEER REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS

Journal Papers

1. Ross, M.W. Relationship between sex role and sex orientation in homosexual men. *New Zealand Psychologist*, 1975, 4(1), 25-29.
2. Ross, M.W. Paradigm lost or paradigm regained? Behaviour modification and homosexuality. *New Zealand Psychologist*, 1977, 6(1), 42-51.
3. Ross, M.W. Societal reaction theory: a phenomenological approach. *Melbourne Psychology Reports*, 1977, 42, 1-17.
4. Ross, M.W., Rogers, L.J., & McCulloch, H. Stigma, sex and society: a new look at gender differentiation and sexual variation. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 1978, 3(4), 315-330.
5. Ross, M.W. The relationship of perceived societal hostility, conformity and psychological adjustment in homosexual males. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 1978, 4(2), 157-168.
6. Ross, M.W. The ethics of animal experimentation: control in practice. *Australian Psychologist*, 1978, 13, 375-378.
7. Ross, M.W. Some possible relationship between brain structure and behaviour in Cetaceans. *Melbourne Psychology Reports*, 1978, 48, 1-18.
8. Ross, M.W., & Talikka, A. Finland and homosexuality. *Psychiatric News*, 1978, 13(14), 2 & 10.
9. Ross, M.W., & Talikka, A. Societal pressure, the homosexual and the role of psychiatry. *Nordisk Psykiatrisk Tidskrift*, 1978, 32, 543-546.
10. Ross, M.W. Brain and behaviour in Cetaceans. *Commission of Inquiry into Whales and Whaling*, Australian Federal Government, 1978, 2, 57-93.
11. Ross, M.W. Bisexuality: fact or fallacy? *British Journal of Sexual Medicine*, 1979, 6(45), 49-50.
12. Ross, M.W. Homosexuality and venereal disease. *British Journal of Sexual Medicine*, 1979, 6(46), 32-33.
13. Ross, M.W. Heterosexual marriage of homosexual males: some associated factors. *Journal of Sex and Marital Therapy*, 1979, 5(2), 142-151.
14. Ross, M.W., & Stålström, O.W. Exorcism as psychiatric treatment: a homosexual case study. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 1979, 8(4), 379-383.
15. Ross, M.W., & Talikka, A. Homosexual labelling and cultural control. *Psychiatric Opinion*, 1979, 16(10), 31-33.
16. Wålinder, J., Lundström, B., Ross, M.W., & Thuwe, I. Transsexualism: incidence, prevalence and sex ratio. *Proceedings of the Sixth International Gender Dysphoria Symposium*, 1979.
17. Sidanius, J., Ekehammar, B., & Ross, M.W. Comparisons of sociopolitical attitudes between democratic societies. *International Journal of Psychology*, 1979, 14, 225-240.
18. Ross, M.W. Why people change their sex: an empirical view. *Australian Left Review*, 1979, October, 71, 21.
19. Ross, M.W. Psychological malpractice and the anti-cult battle: the brain wash. *Australian Journal of Social Issues*, 1979, 14, 201-210.

20. Ross, M.W. Retrospective distortion in homosexual research. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 1980, 9, 523-531.
21. Orr, K., & Ross, M.W. Homosexuality in clinical and biblical context. *Journal of Christian Education*. 1980, 69, 37-48.
22. Andrew, G.M., & Ross, M.W. A short form of the Bem Sex Role Inventory. *Journal of Psychiatric Treatment and Evaluation*, 1981, 3, 563-566.
23. Ross, M.W., Wålinder, J., Lundström, B., & Thuwe, I. Cross-cultural approaches to transsexualism: a comparison between Sweden and Australia. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 1981, 63, 75-82.
24. Ross, M.W. The ethics of experiments on higher animals. *Social Science and Medicine*, 1981, 15F, 52-61.*
25. Ross, M.W. Attitudes of male homosexuals to venereal disease clinics. *Medical Journal of Australia*, 1981, 2, 670-671.
26. Ross, M.W. Social factors in homosexually acquired venereal disease: a comparison between Sweden and Australia. *British Journal of Venereal Diseases*, 1982, 58, 263-268.
27. Ross, M.W. Some effects of heterosexual marriage on homosexual desire. *Australian Journal of Sex, Marriage and Family*, 1982, 3(1), 25-29.
28. Ross, M.W. The ethics of animal experimentation in medicine. *New Doctor*, 1982, 24, 12-13.
29. Badcock, K.A., & Ross, M.W. Neuropsychological testing of Australian Aborigines. *Australian Psychologist*, 1982, 17, 297-299.
30. Ross, M.W., Campbell, R.L., & Clayer, J.R. New inventory for measurement of parental rearing patterns: an English form of the EMBU. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 1982, 66, 499-507.
31. Ross, M.W. Societal relationships and gender role in homosexuals: a cross-cultural comparison. *Journal of Sex Research*, 1983, 19, 273-288.
32. Ross, M.W. Clinical profiles of Hare Krishna devotees. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 1983, 140, 416-420.
33. Ross, M.W., Kalucy, R.S., & Morton, J.E. Locus of control in obesity: predictors of success in a jaw-wiring programme. *British Journal of Medical Psychology*, 1983, 56, 49-56.
34. Ross, M.W. Counselling the homosexual patient. *Patient Management*, 1983, 7(7), 117-123.
35. Ross, M.W. Mental health and membership of the Hare Krishnas: a case study. *Australian Psychologist*, 1983, 18, 128-129.
36. Ross, M.W. Homosexuality and social sex roles: a re-evaluation. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 1983, 9(1), 1-6.*
37. Ross, M.W. Femininity, masculinity and sexual orientation: some cross cultural relationships. *Journal of Homosexuality*, 1983, 9(1), 27-36.*
38. Hafner, R.J., & Ross, M.W. Predicting the outcome of behavior therapy for agoraphobia. *Behavior Research and Therapy*, 1983, 21, 375-382.
39. Ross, M.W., Clayer, J.R., & Campbell, R.L. Parental rearing patterns and suicidal thoughts. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 1983, 67, 429-433.
40. Ross, M.W. Predictive value of selection interviews in success in first year medicine. *Medical Journal of Australia*, 1983, 2, 423-424.
41. Adcock, N.V., & Ross, M.W. Early memories, early experiences and personality. *Social Behaviour and Personality*, 1983, 11, 95-100.
42. Ross, M.W., Clayer, J.R., & Campbell, R.L. Dimensions of child-rearing practices: factor structure of the EMBU. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 1983, 68, 476-483.

43. Campbell, R.L., Clayer, J.R., & Ross, M.W. An Australian standardisation of the Eysenck Personality Questionnaire. *Australian Council for Educational Research Bulletin*, 1983, 34, 22-25.
44. Ross, M.W., & Need, J.A. Teaching sexual medicine: the Flinders curriculum. *British Journal of Sexual Medicine*, 1984, 11, 94-96.
45. Ross, M.W. Problems with research on Hare Krishna Devotees. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 1984, 141,144.
46. Ross, M.W. Intelligence testing in Australian Aborigines. *Comparative Education*, 1984, 20, 371-375.
47. Clayer, J.R., Campbell, R.L., & Ross, M.W. Parental rearing and transient thought disorder in young adults. *Psychopathology*, 1984, 17, 9-16.
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Appendix 5: Declaration of Confidentiality

DECLARATION OF CONFIDENTIALITY AND DATA PRIVACY

(to be signed by all persons involved in the 1st Global LGBT Foundation and UNAIDS Survey on Happiness, Sex and Quality of life)

I will be bound by all the terms and conditions of the confidentiality undertaking signed by the duly designated representative of my research entity and will use the dataset indicated in the research proposal in accordance with the terms of use attached to the confidentiality undertaking.

I understand that I must treat all data related to the LGBTI Global Survey in accordance with the EU Directive 95/46/EC and as amended, replaced or superseded from time to time, including by the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR)

I will:

- (a) use the dataset only for the purposes specified in the research proposal;
- (b) safeguard the dataset and any usernames and passwords associated with it;
- (c) ensure that any results of analyses will not be disclosive or potentially disclosive in conjunction with other publicly available information;
- (d) acknowledge the dataset and its source in any research report or publication and also state that the results and conclusions are mine and not those of the LGBT Foundation, UNAIDS, Aix-Marseille University or University of Minnesota;
- (e) provide the LGBT Foundation and UNAIDS with references to publications and other research reports based on this dataset;
- (f) preserve the confidentiality of information pertaining to identifiable individuals, households and/or organisations, such as those using the email address provided in the survey to exercise their right of withdrawal;
- (g) submit the final complete output of my work for the confidentiality check to the competent LGBT Foundation or UNAIDS staff (in case of access to secure use files);
- (h) destroy the dataset and any data or variables derived from it at the end of the research period specified in the research proposal and sign a declaration to the effect that it has been ensured that all data have been destroyed;
- (i) abide by any other conditions notified to me by LGBT Foundation and UNAIDS (e.g. guidelines for publication);
- (j) inform the LGBT Foundation and UNAIDS immediately about any breach of the confidentiality rules laid down in the confidentiality undertaking or in the terms of use of confidential data for scientific purposes.

I will not:

- (a) use the data (scientific use files) outside the premises of my research entity;
- (b) allow non-authorized users to access the dataset (authorized users are named in the research proposal);
- (c) use the data for research purposes before it is checked for confidentiality by the LGBT Foundation and UNAIDS (in case of access to secure use files)
- (d) remove the data or any part of it (in case of access to secure use files);
- (e) attempt to link the data to other (including public) datasets, whether or not provided by the LGBT Foundation and UNAIDS, if not expressly agreed;
- (f) attempt to identify any individual record (individual, household, business, etc.) in the dataset, or claim to have done so;

(g) release or publish any information or results which identify any individual record or may lead to the identification of any individual record.

I certify that I have read all of the above clauses, that I understand that I am accountable for correct and responsible use of the data and data access system, and that I understand that if I fail to comply with these clauses, my access to the dataset will be withdrawn and I will be liable to any other sanctions that may be determined by my research entity or are specified in the applicable civil or penal law.

Name:**Signature:****Date:**

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